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Regioselective layer-by-layer coating of colloidal silica

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ABSTRACT

Regioselective layer-by-layer coating of colloidal silica

Anisotropic metal nanoparticles show promising features for catalysis, chemical and biological sensors or theranostics. Such anisotropic silver patches on colloidal silica are synthesised, processed and investigated in this current thesis with the goal of introducing a regioselective polyelectrolyte coating to the silica in addition to the silver patch.

The silver patchy particles were synthesised by a modified Tollens process and functionalised with dodecanethiol which acts as a protective layer. The functionalised particles were then coated with PDADMAC using the layer-by-layer technique. The effect of varying coating time, salt type added to the polyelectrolyte solution as well as different salt concentrations was studied. Based on these results, a layer-by-layer coating procedure compatible with silver patchy particles was successfully established. The regioselectivity of the coating was shown by heterocoagulation with oppositely charged magnetite nanoparticles.

The feasibility of a PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC multilayer was demonstrated, however, an improvement to a single polyelectrolyte layer was not noticeable. As a preparation for self-organisation studies, the size of regioselectively coated surface has been tuned indirectly by adjusting the silver patch size distribution. Mixing of coated and uncoated particles led to agglomeration, but no ordered self-organisation could be observed in an optical microscopy set-up, partly attributed to the limited magnification.

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Symbols and abbreviations

$^{\circ}\text{C}$ <i>degree Celsius</i>	LSP <i>localised surface plasmon</i>
μL <i>microlitre</i>	LSPR <i>localised surface plasmon resonance</i>
μm <i>micrometre</i>	M <i>molar</i>
Ag <i>silver</i>	mg <i>milligram</i>
Ag^+ <i>silver ion</i>	MH <i>6-mercapto-1-hexanol</i>
Ag_2O <i>silver oxide</i>	min <i>minute</i>
AgCl <i>silver chloride</i>	mL <i>millilitre</i>
AgNO_3 <i>silver nitrate</i>	mm <i>millimetre</i>
AgP <i>silver patchy particle sample</i>	mM <i>millimolar</i>
AgPF <i>functionalised silver patchy particle sample</i>	mRNA <i>messenger ribonucleic acid</i>
AgPFPE <i>functionalised and PDADMAC coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	ms <i>millisecond</i>
AgPFPE2 <i>functionalised and with two polyelectrolyte layers (PSS/PDADMAC) coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	mV <i>millivolt</i>
AgPFPE3 <i>functionalised and with three polyelectrolyte layers (PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC) coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	MW <i>molecular weight</i>
AgPFPEI <i>functionalised and PEI coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	NH_3 <i>ammonia</i>
AgPPE <i>PDADMAC coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	nm <i>nanometre</i>
AgPPEI <i>PEI coated silver patchy particle sample</i>	NP <i>nanoparticle</i>
Au <i>gold</i>	O_2 <i>oxygen</i>
BF <i>brightfield</i>	OH <i>hydroxy</i>
CH_2O <i>formaldehyde</i>	OHP <i>outer Helmholtz plane</i>
Cl^- <i>chloride ion</i>	PDADMAC
cm <i>centimetre</i>	<i>poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride)</i>
d <i>diameter (particle size)</i>	PE <i>polyelectrolyte</i>
Da <i>Dalton</i>	PEI <i>poly(ethylene imine)</i>
DDT <i>dodecanethiol</i>	PSS <i>poly(sodium 4-styrene-sulfonate)</i>
DF <i>darkfield</i>	rcf <i>relative centrifugal force</i>
DNA <i>desoxyribonucleic acid</i>	RT <i>room temperature</i>
EtOH <i>ethanol</i>	s <i>second</i>
Fe_3O_4 <i>iron oxide, magnetite</i>	S <i>sulphur</i>
g <i>gram</i>	SE <i>secondary electrons</i>
h <i>hour</i>	SEM <i>scanning electron microscopy, scanning electron microscope</i>
H_2S <i>hydrogen sulphide</i>	Si <i>silicon</i>
HAADF <i>high angle annular darkfield</i>	SiO_2 <i>silica</i>
HCOOH <i>formic acid</i>	STEM <i>scanning transmission electron microscopy, scanning transmission electron microscope</i>
k <i>Boltzmann constant</i>	T <i>temperature</i>
KCl <i>potassium chloride</i>	TG <i>thermogravimetry</i>
KNO_3 <i>potassium nitrate</i>	UV-Vis <i>ultraviolet-visible</i>
kV <i>kilovolt</i>	UV-Vis-NIR <i>ultraviolet-visible-near infrared</i>
LbL <i>layer-by-layer</i>	v/v <i>volume fraction</i>
	VdW <i>Van-der-Waals</i>
	wt% <i>percentage by mass (weight percent)</i>
	ϵ <i>permittivity / dielectric constant</i>
	κ <i>Debye-Hückel parameter</i>

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1 Introduction

Given the current events in the COVID-19 pandemic and the breakthrough in finding and producing two effective vaccines using messenger ribonucleic acid (mRNA), another research on mRNA treatment for Multiple Sclerosis by the BioNTech corporation has drawn great attention. In both cases, a nanoparticulate formulation involving liposomal nanoparticles (NP) plays a crucial role for a safe and efficient delivery of mRNA to its target cells [1, 2].

Though being considered the most flexible nanoparticulate delivery system for drugs [3], liposomal NPs are but a fraction of developed and researched nanocarriers. The materials used to produce those NPs cover a wide range, e.g. polymers, mesoporous and inorganic materials [4]. This variety and the diversity in properties make NPs and nanoparticulate systems highly interesting not only for alternative drug delivery approaches and so-called theranostics, but also explains the great appeal of NPs for other applications such as heterogenous catalysis or chemical and biological sensors [5, 6]. The high surface-to-volume ratio in NPs and, therefore, a turnover comparable to homogenous catalysts makes them attractive since the advantageous handling and recyclability of heterogenous catalysts are maintained. Especially metal NPs exhibit promising catalytic traits, showing different electronic properties compared to the bulk [7]. This electronic behaviour also makes metal NPs candidates for enhanced sensors, as mentioned above, based on an effect known as localised surface plasmon resonance (LSPR). LSPR is, *inter alia*, dependent on the surrounding medium and can thus indicate changes therein, detecting e.g. changing gas compositions or presence of certain biomolecules [5, 8].

The optical properties of the metal NPs are furthermore highly dependent on particle size and shape, with the sphere being the simplest morphology [9, 10]. Anisotropic metal NPs like discs, rods or shells show unique properties compared to their dense spherical counterparts. Nanorods, for example, show two resonance wavelengths related to the long and short axis of the rod [11]. Another kind of complex anisotropic NPs are hybrid NPs consisting of at least two components. The structures of such hybrids range from core-shell particles to dumbbell shapes and tipped nanorods. The

involved materials can be of organic, e.g. fullerenes, or inorganic origin like metals or silica [12–14]. In case of anisotropic metal hybrid NPs, the dielectric environment becomes asymmetric, for instance, when metal NPs are directly synthesised on a substrate [10]. The research group around R. N. Klupp Taylor at the Institute of particle technology (*Lehrstuhl für Feststoff- und Grenzflächenverfahrenstechnik*) has developed a facile one-pot synthesis for such anisotropic hybrid particles. Silver (Ag) is deposited on silica (SiO₂) nanospheres by a modified Tollens reaction [15]. The Ag does not cover the whole SiO₂ sphere and forms one or more continuously coated regions. Such particles are referred to as patchy particles. The research group has further determined parameters that enable the tuning of the patch morphology from cup-like to dendritic, which affects the optical properties [16]. This approach was also used to synthesise gold (Au) patches on silica at preformed Ag patches as seeds and transferred to seedless formation of dendritic Au patches on polystyrene [17, 18]. The synthesis of these metallic patchy particles was developed as a batch process but continuous flow synthesis with a T-mixer set-up has been developed and is currently further investigated [19]. A scale up of the batch process leads to wider size distributions as the critical mixing time cannot be controlled as well as in smaller reaction volumes. A continuous synthesis, however, allows for significant scale up while patch morphology, size and yield can be tuned more accurately [19].

The current work investigates further processing of Ag patchy particles and the feasibility of regioselective coating with polyelectrolytes (PE) in a batch process, exploiting the layer-by-layer (LbL) technique. The particles are therefore prepared for coating by functionalising them with dodecanethiol (DDT) and the LbL technique is applied with poly(diallyldimethylammonium chloride) (PDADMAC) and poly(sodium 4-styrene-sulfonate) (PSS). The variation of the electrolyte, which is added to the coating solution, the electrolyte concentration and different coating times are studied. The general compatibility of the PEs with the Ag patch is determined to establish a coating procedure tailored to the Ag patchy particles. The regioselectivity of the PE layer is verified by magnetite adsorption and, lastly, the self-organisation of the particles mediated by the PE layer is checked.

2 Fundamentals

The following section provides general information and theory related to the fundamentals explaining the chemistry behind the silver patchy particle synthesis and functionalisation. Particle interactions are described, giving insight into the particle attributes affecting coating and self-assembly. Further, the origin of optical properties of colloidal silica and metal NPs will be explained since they play a major role in analysing the prepared samples.

2.1 Particle interactions in colloidal systems

Particle interactions in solution are highly complex and depend on several internal and external influences such as particle composition, solvent or additives like salts. Several models and theories exist to explain the observed behaviour of particles in colloidal systems.

2.1.1 Electrical diffuse double layer

Particles and colloids commonly carry charges on their surfaces. These often depend on the pH of the surrounding aqueous solvent or, analogously, the activity of the ions as is the case for silver halides. For varying pH, the particles will express different potentials due to a difference in surface charge density. At certain pH levels they show no charge or potential at all. This is the result of protonation or deprotonation of surface groups in acidic or alkaline solutions, respectively. The counterions, which compensate surface charge, form a layer around the particles [20]. The Helmholtz model describes this layer of counterions at a charged surface approximated for planar surfaces. Over time, it has been further developed, bringing forth the Gouy-Chapman model, which holds true only for dilute solutions, the Stern model, where ions are not treated as point charges anymore [21], and Bockris-Müller-Devanathan model, that includes specific adsorption and solvent effects [22]. In this section, the electrical diffuse double layer will be explained for spherical particles. The potential and scheme of the double layer is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Electric diffuse double layer around a spherical, positively charged particle and the corresponding electric potential Ψ with distance x from the particle surface. S is the Stern layer from the particle surface to the outer Helmholtz plane, consisting of anions close to the particle surface that can be seen as bound. The Debye length κ^{-1} expresses the thickness of the double layer. Solvent molecules are not depicted. Adapted from [23, 24].

Independent of the mechanism that leads to the colloidal particles carrying charges on their surface, counterions in the solvent with opposite charge will be attracted to the particle surface and accumulate while the co-ion concentration will be comparably low as co-ions are being repelled. Usually, the particle surface charge is expressed as a potential difference with the electroneutral bulk solution as reference where the potential is set to zero [23]. The layer of counterions adsorbed to the particle surface is called Stern layer. The counterions in this layer can be treated as ionically bound and move with the particle, e.g. in an applied external electrical field. The Stern layer ends at the outer Helmholtz plane (OHP) which marks the adsorbed counterions in their solvation shell. Most counterions are thus not in direct contact to the particle surface and maintain a distance corresponding to the solvation or, in the case of aqueous solutions, hydration shells. Specific adsorption is an exception to this. The farther away from the surface, the more diffuse the ions are distributed as the potential difference to the bulk declines and the Brownian motion becomes more and

more prevalent. This diffuse layer has a thickness of κ^{-1} , called the Debye length. The Debye-Hückel parameter κ depends on the electrolyte used in the solution, its concentration and the permittivity or dielectric constant ϵ [23, 25]. The conformation of two differently charged layers, i.e. the particle surface and the surrounding counterion layer in the immediate surface vicinity, acts like a capacitor as in the Helmholtz model. Thus, the potential decreases linearly in the bound layer as depicted in Figure 1. The decrease in potential in the diffuse layer is in relation to the Poisson-Boltzmann equation. This equation takes the statistical distribution of the ions into account as well as the distribution of charges in an electrical field [21, 23, 26].

Upon motion of the particle, the loosely bound molecules and ions in the diffuse layer are sheared against a strongly bound layer including the Stern layer. The resulting shear plane, or shear layer, is located between the OHP and the Gouy plane, the “border” of the diffuse layer, and is thinner than κ^{-1} [27]. The potential at this shear plane is called the zeta potential and can be determined by e.g. measuring the electrophoretic mobility of the particles in a dispersion (see section 3.2.2). The shear plane is conventionally presumed to be located near the Stern layer [23], though in recent years it was suggested that the distance between the Stern layer and the shear plane may be larger and the shear plane might be located closer to the Gouy plane than the Stern layer [24, 28].

2.1.2 Stability of dispersions and DLVO-theory

The surface charges and resulting electrical diffuse double layers around particles contribute to the stability and instability of particle dispersions. The model of the electrical double layer is integrated in the DLVO-theory (named after Derjaguin, Landau, Verwey and Overbeek). This theory describes the overlapping attractive and repulsive forces between particles and thus the electrostatic stability of dispersions. It has to be noted that this theory does not take into account all existing effects in dispersions, but in its simplicity it allows for interpretation of colloidal system behaviour and will be introduced as such: a model containing the essential contributing forces in colloid stability [29, 30].

The attractive Van-der-Waals (VdW) forces and repulsive electrostatic forces for equal charges are treated additively. The VdW forces are long range forces and comprise the interactions between two dipoles (Keesom), the dipole – induced dipole interactions (Debye) and the dispersive London force, interactions between two induced dipoles [25]. As these VdW forces are of attractive character, they are assigned a negative value when plotting the interaction energy between particles. The short ranged electrostatic forces carry a positive sign. A contribution to the DLVO theory has been the addition of the Born repulsion, which prevents overlapping of atoms due to Pauli's exclusion principle. This, however, has little effect on the stability of the dispersion itself [20]. Nonetheless, the Born repulsion is depicted in Figure 2 together with the VdW attraction and electrostatic repulsion.

Figure 2: Schematic graph of the interaction energy between two equally charged particles according to the DLVO theory. (1) Primary minimum; (2) Maximum/Energy barrier; (3) Secondary minimum. Adapted from [20, 31].

The attractive force declines with a steeper slope with increasing distance from the surface than the electrostatic repulsion. However, the attraction is stronger close to the surface. A primary minimum (1) in the net interaction energy is the result. Further away from the surface, the repulsion dominates and leads to a maximum (2) in net

interaction energy. The interaction energy then declines and reaches a secondary minimum (3). Kinetically stable flocculates can form at this distance for certain particle sizes, but they are easily redispersed [20]. For a high enough maximum ($> 25 k T$), the particles cannot overcome the energy barrier and do not aggregate into the primary minimum[25]. This maximum, however, is sensitive to electrolytes in the dispersion and decreases with salt concentration until it disappears completely. That salt concentration, at which aggregation or coagulation occurs, is called critical coagulation concentration. This is owed to the decrease in electric diffuse double layer thickness as charges are screened more. When the electrical diffuse double layers of particles overlap, the ion concentration increases between the particles. Repulsive interactions arise as a consequence and osmotic pressure leads to a flux of water molecules, pushing the particles away from each other [20, 23]. However, with smaller double layers, the particles can get closer more easily.

Other than through charge stabilisation, particles can be stabilised sterically by oligomers and polymers grafted on the particle surface. These act as spacers between the particles. In a solvent with favourable monomer-solvent interaction, the adsorbates take an elongated conformation. As mixing with themselves is less favoured, other grafted particles are kept at a distance. Upon an overlap or compression of the polymer chains when particles come close to each other, the entropy would be reduced due to less available volume per chain, which also induces repulsive forces [23, 25]. When the polymers or oligomers carry charges themselves, they additionally show electrostatic repulsion, hence particles are stabilised electrosterically.

2.2 Material specific chemistry of colloidal silica and silver patchy particles

Within this present work, the inherent surface properties of SiO_2 play a role during Ag patch synthesis as well as the planned LbL coating. The surface properties of SiO_2 and the chemistry behind the Ag patches will be presented in this section.

2.2.1 Surface properties of silica

The surface OH-groups (silanol) of colloidal SiO_2 are formed during the condensation of $\text{Si}(\text{OH})_4$ as not all OH-groups of the precursor react. Upon drying, the physisorbed and chemisorbed water is removed and Si – O – Si bridges (siloxane) can be formed. Thermally treated, dried SiO_2 rehydroxylates in water, forming OH-groups. Silicon (Si) atoms prefer a tetrahedral molecular conformation as center atoms. This is not given for the conformation of siloxane at the particle surface, promoting the formation of the silanol groups. Siloxane groups can be further affected by still present neighbouring silanol groups that mediate the chemisorption of water molecules [32, 33]. Surface groups in general and after rehydroxylation are schematically depicted in Figure 3 according to the Zhuravlev model [32].

Figure 3: Schematic depiction of the surface of amorphous colloidal silica; a) possible surface groups, clockwise: siloxane, vicinal silanols with hydrogen bond, isolated silanols, geminal silanols; b) rehydroxylated silica surface. Adapted from [32].

Removal of the surface silanol groups by drying the colloidal particles at certain temperatures eventually leads to condensation of those groups and O-bridge formation between the Si, thus siloxane groups are presented at the surface. With declining amount of silanol groups, the surface becomes less hydrophilic. This makes

it clear that the presence or absence of those silanol groups determines the surface properties of colloidal SiO₂ [32]. The composition of silica surface groups, in turn, also depends on the thermal “history” of the particles. Physisorbed and chemisorbed water molecules desorb at different temperatures, i.e. in different steps of drying. These steps and corresponding temperatures were determined by thermogravimetric (TG) measurement by Zhuravlev [32] and further studied by Peng *et al.* [33] with TG, differential calorimetry and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy. The main steps with rising temperature can be divided into three phases:

- I) Desorption of multi- and monolayers of physisorbed water
- II) Disappearance of chemisorbed vicinal silanol groups and onset of desorption of internal OH-groups
- III) Removal of all silanol groups and internal OH-groups, formation of siloxane

The surface of the SiO₂ can be easily rehydroxylated after phase I and II. After phase III, the dehydroxylation is still reversible, but slow. The sintering and shrinkage of particles occur in addition to the dehydration and dehydroxylation.

Furthermore, the Si-atoms are not evenly distributed at the particle surface and thus the silanol groups are not equidistant to each other. As the interactions between the groups and the surrounding water molecules can vary due to the forementioned distribution of surface groups, the individual groups show different adsorption and reaction behaviour. Impurities also cause altered surface properties and have to be considered separately [32, 33].

The presence of silanol groups also makes the SiO₂ particle surface in water sensitive to pH changes. Upon introduction of protons in acidic and hydroxide ions in alkaline medium, a significant amount of the silanol can be protonated or deprotonated, leaving either Si – OH₂⁺ or Si – O⁻ groups, respectively. This happens analogously to geminal silanols. Protonation of siloxane groups can lead to the breakage of the Si – OH⁺ – Si bond when reacting with present water molecules, yielding new silanol groups [34]. SiO₂ NPs generally have a negative surface charge with the point of zero

charge at a low pH [35]. At constant salt concentration, the charge density increases (more negative charge per surface area) with increasing pH as more and more silanol groups become deprotonated. The zeta potential shows different behaviour depending on high or low salt concentrations, as the effect of the electrical diffuse double layer must be considered. At high salt concentrations (> 100 mM), the zeta potential becomes more negative with increasing pH for moderate pH values and shows little to no further change in the regions of extreme acidic or alkaline pH. In a solution with low salt concentration (< 100 mM), the electric double layer is thicker than at high concentrations, affecting the zeta potential. From low pH to high pH, the zeta potential first decreases, i.e. becomes more negative, passes a minimum (highest absolute value) and increases again [35, 36]. Apart from external influences, the particle size, which essentially determines the curvature, and surface roughness cause a deviation of charge density on particles compared to a flat surface [37, 38]. These changes in charge and potential for different pH, salt concentrations and particle sizes cause the SiO₂ particles to show altered stability, affinities and interactions with other molecules and particles.

2.2.2 Silver patch synthesis

Patchy particles are an attractive research field due to their anisotropic properties as they can find many possible applications, such as in biomedicine or catalysis. Klupp Taylor *et al.* [15, 16] have investigated and established a facile way of synthesising such Ag patches on spherical SiO₂ particles without the need of prior functionalisation of the SiO₂ or seeding.

The one-pot synthesis of the Ag patches on SiO₂ spheres basically follows the Tollens reaction, also called silver mirror reaction, with formaldehyde (CH₂O) as a reducing agent instead of a reducing sugar [39]. This reaction takes place in an aqueous alkaline environment achieved by addition of ammonia (NH₃) (equation (1)).

Raising the pH, NH₃ moves the equilibrium of the oxidation reaction of CH₂O towards formic acid (HCOOH) [16]. In this course, silver ions (Ag⁺) are reduced (equation (2)).

NH_3 not only promotes the anodic partial reaction, but it also complexes the Ag^+ and coordinates it to the SiO_2 surface. On the one hand, the positively charged complex is attracted to the negatively charged silanol groups [40]. On the other hand, the complex shows a specific geometry and directionality [41] and enhances the accumulation of Ag^+ near the SiO_2 surface via H-bonds in addition to the electrostatic attraction [16]. Eventually, heterogenous nucleation takes place at the SiO_2 surface due to supersaturation of Ag^+ and as the ions are already located at the particle surface, Ag growth takes place at the patch edges, covering more SiO_2 instead of protruding from the surface.

Figure 4: Examples of a) cup-like Ag patches and b) dendritic Ag patches on spherical 500 nm SiO_2 particles, 50 k magnification, 10 kV.

The patch morphology changes from cup-like dense patches at higher NH_3 concentration (17 mM) to dendritic at lower NH_3 concentration (1 mM). Representative dense and dendritic patches are shown in Figure 4. As the ammonia-complexed Ag^+ shows lower reactivity than plain Ag^+ [42], the reduction of Ag^+ is slower for high NH_3 concentrations than for lower ones. Furthermore, the different silver ammine complex species (mono- and di-ammine) are in equilibrium with each other as well as with non-complexed Ag^+ , which depends on the NH_3 concentration. For higher NH_3 concentrations, more Ag^+ is complexed and due to the lower reactivity, the patch formation is integration limited and yields cup-like shapes with smooth edges. As for low NH_3 concentration, the patch growth is diffusion limited since the reduction reaction is more rapid for non-complexed Ag^+ , yielding a dendritic morphology [16]. Especially the cup-like patch morphology raises interest here as it

is a potential template for regioselective enhancements of these already patchy particles.

2.2.3 Thiol-affinity to noble metals

Bulk silver is known to easily tarnish, visible in old silverware or jewellery. The cause of this effect is mainly the reaction with atmospheric oxygen (O_2), but such tarnishing also occurs when Ag reacts with sulphur (S) species, e.g. hydrogen sulphide (H_2S). O_2 still plays a mediating role in this reaction as is seen in equation (3) [43, 44].

Ag^+ ions form complexes with thiols. The complex is thermodynamically preferred as is apparent from the stability or formation constant with pK_f around 13, indicating strong binding [44–46]. For Ag NPs, a process starting with physisorption of the thiol, a transition state and final chemisorption is likely (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Schematic depiction of energy levels during thiol ($R-S-H$) adsorption to an Ag particle from physisorbed state to chemisorbed state. Adapted from [47].

The formation of the transition state is energetically higher than the physisorbed thiol and consequently an activation energy is necessary for the chemisorption. The chemisorbed thiol on Ag ($R-S-Ag$), however, is energetically more favoured. It is thus the conception that thiols adsorbed to noble metals do not desorb easily [47]. With sufficient thiol concentration and exposure time, the $R-S-Ag$ layer can transform into a shell consisting of a mixture of $R-S-Ag$ and Ag_2S complexes which

prevent ion release, passivating the surface and thus inhibit further Ag oxidation [44, 48, 49]. Using these properties of thiols, self-assembled thiol monolayers can be generated on noble metal surfaces, such as Ag NPs [49, 50].

Au NPs grafted via thiol groups have already found applications in mostly biomedical fields. They can be used in imaging or colorimetric sensing for e.g. diagnostics. Hazardous heavy metal ions, which are a risk to public health, can be detected with Au NPs that are functionalised with 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid or with NPs functionalised with thiolated desoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) [51, 52]. Another topical example are immunochromatographic assays like those currently used for the rapid COVID-19 tests for blood serum or nasal swabs. These test strips contain colloidal Au that is conjugated to either a SARS-CoV-2 antigen (antibody test) or monoclonal antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 (antigen test) [53, 54]. The conjugation of either antigens or antibodies to Au NPs can be achieved via various interactions. The chemisorption through thiol groups already present in antibodies or biomolecules is one of those interactions. Furthermore, thiol derivatives can function as linkers for antigen or antibody adsorption [55].

2.3 Optical properties of silica nano-spheres and silver patchy particles

15 causes of colour were identified by Nassau [56], among them are colour from metals and metal NPs and colour from scattering. These two causes will be briefly presented in this section as they apply to the patchy particles synthesised in this work and the resulting optical properties were exploited for the characterisation of the particles.

2.3.1 Surface plasmon resonance of noble metals

Metals, such as noble metals used in electronic devices and jewellery, are well known to exhibit a metallic sheen as bulk material. However, it is not common knowledge, that the same noble metals are responsible for the colour of old stained glasses that were used for windows of many churches or coloured glassware. These colours such

as red and yellow are the result of so called surface plasmon resonance in Au and Ag NPs [57].

The conductivity of metals can be explained by their delocalised electrons which also play a role in their optical properties. Upon bonding of two alike atoms, meaning the combination of atom orbitals of equal energy level, two discrete orbitals develop. Those are a bonding orbital with lower energy and an antibonding orbital at higher energy level. The bonding valence electrons then occupy these molecular orbitals. Considering, that trillions of atoms are present in just one cubic centimetre of metal, trillions of molecular orbitals are to be expected. The distance between the individual energy levels of those orbitals becomes so small that they can be practically seen as a continuous energy band. The number of electrons occupying this energy band is the sum of the valence electrons of all involved individual atoms. These electrons “fill” the energy band from the lowest energy level with the highest occupied energy level at absolute zero called Fermi level or Fermi energy. The electrons then belong to the whole collective and not to individual atoms, thus they are delocalised [56, 58].

Light, as an electromagnetic wave, can excite the electrons below the Fermi level to higher levels in the energy band. A negative charge above the Fermi level and a positively charged “hole” emerges in the energy band because of the now missing electron. As light below a certain frequency (plasma frequency) is absorbed strongly by metals, it can only penetrate a few hundred atoms into the bulk, less than a single wavelength. The infalling light induces alternating electric currents at the metal surface, a displacement of the oscillating electrons from their equilibrium position, which reemit the light immediately, leading to the metallic reflection and sheen. A specific type of oscillation at the bulk metal surface are surface plasmon polaritons. They can only occur at the interface of the metal and the surrounding medium due to the change in refractive index [56, 58, 59].

When the electrons are confined to a metal particle much smaller than the wavelength of the incident light, i.e. in NPs, the oscillation is distributed over the whole particle. The displacement of the electron cloud against the positively charged lattice, i.e. the metal NP, creates a restoring force much like a spring. These plasmons are called localised surface plasmons (LSP). The LSP can only be excited by light at a frequency which is in resonance with this oscillation. This frequency is then called the LSPR. For

small particles, it oscillates like a dipole parallel to the electric field of the light [10, 59]. The maximum in the optical extinction of the metal NP, visualised for instance in ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy, is located at the LSPR frequency. The resonance condition is fulfilled in the visible region for Au and Ag, yielding the gold-ruby red or the silver-yellow (Figure 9, right) of respective NPs [56, 60]. A schematic of the LSPR is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Schematic of the LSPR in a metal NP. The plasmons oscillate in the light wavelength which corresponds to their resonance frequency. Taken from [61].

Generally, the size and shape of the metal NP influence the LSPR and, thus, the optical properties. Larger or non-spherical particles will generally have multiple resonances, such as in nanorods, nanodiscs or triangular nanoprisms[10]. These kinds of shapes are also called anisotropic. Modelled extinction spectra of such triangular Ag nanoprisms with snipped off tips and measured absorbance spectrum of Ag semi-nanoshells can be seen in Figure 7. In each spectrum, several peaks are visible for a specific Ag NP shape. The spectra contain multiple peaks that belong to multipole modes of Ag and to in-plane and out-of-plane resonances. These further depend on the particle morphology, e.g. short axis and long axis of a rod or triangular prism or the thickness and diameter of cups or semi-shells. Furthermore, the dielectric environment affects the LSPR, as the ratio of surface to volume is high in NPs and a significant fraction of atoms is located at the surface of the NP with contact to the surrounding medium. Moreover, chemical interactions at the NP surface may also

change the LSPR by e.g. changing the dielectric environment itself or through a withdrawal of electrons from the energy band by forming chemical bonds [9, 59].

Figure 7: Measured absorbance spectrum of 20 nm thick Ag semi-shells with 200 nm inner diameter in CH_2Cl_2 and simulated extinction efficiencies of a) smooth semi-shells, b) tapered semi-shells and c) tapered semi-shells with loose material not removed as for b (left). Two broad and one sharp peaks can be distinguished in the measured spectrum. Taken from [62]; Measured and simulated extinction spectra of triangular Ag nanoprisms with tips snipped off and with water as the dielectric medium (right). The calculated spectrum is averaged over all possible prism orientations. Three peaks in total are visible, belonging to multipole resonances in the particle. Taken from [10].

2.3.2 Light scattering by silica particles

Small particles like dust scatter the light and thus the path of sunbeams becomes visible. These dust particles usually are not smaller than the wavelengths present in sunlight. However, scattering can also occur without any particles present. Fluctuations in medium density and refractive index scatter light in a similar fashion. Those fluctuations are caused by the motion and collisions of molecules in gases or defects in crystals or glass.[56, 58]. This section will only cover elastic scattering caused by particles, since Ag patchy particles are studied.

In case of a single particle, the incident light, an electromagnetic wave, influences the electric charges in the particle. In that way induced dipole moments located throughout the whole particle oscillate with the same frequency as the light exciting them. They reradiate the light in every direction, thus the light is being scattered [63]. Particles smaller than the wavelength of visible light scatter blue stronger than red, as the shorter wavelengths of the blue are closer to their natural oscillation frequency. Therefore, the resonance is stronger and the colour perceived by such scattering is a hue of blue. This is called Rayleigh scattering. When particles reach the size close to

the wavelength of the light, forward scattering becomes more intense (Figure 8). In such case, different colours can be detected at certain scattering angles only for monodisperse particle collectives. With increasing polydispersity and particle size, the scattered light looks white. The Mie theory presents a way to describe the scattering of spherical particles in that size range [56, 58, 63].

Figure 8: Schematical distribution of scattered light by particles of different sizes. Rayleigh scattering for particles much smaller than the wavelength, Debye scattering for particles with size similar to the wavelength and Mie scattering for particles larger than the wavelength. Debye scattering is often combined into Mie scattering. Taken from [64].

However, it must be noted that the analysed Ag patchy particles consist of two different materials and are of anisotropic character. This leads to further individual scattering effects in addition to the LSPR by the Ag patches (scattering and absorption of light) [63]. Nonetheless, the scattering of SiO_2 must be considered when handling UV-Vis and near infrared (UV-Vis-NIR) spectra of these particles regarding the extinction intensities. Individual spectra of silica and colloidal Ag NPs are shown in Figure 9 as comparison to the extinction spectra of the anisotropic patchy particles synthesised in this work.

Figure 9: Extinction spectrum of 500 nm silica measured in water (left) and absorption spectra of Ag NPs of different sizes and measured in dispersion as obtained after synthesis using gallic acid (right). Taken from [65].

2.4 Polyelectrolyte multilayers by layer-by-layer deposition

The LbL deposition technique presented by Decher *et. al.* [66, 67] is a method for the formation of, initially, multilayers of amphiphiles and later alternating polyanions and polycations on planar surfaces. Nowadays it is extended to a variety of materials like biomolecules, such as DNA and proteins, organic and inorganic compounds or colloids [66, 67]. The principle of LbL deposition on flat surfaces is depicted in Figure 10.

An easy set-up of several beakers with PE solutions and washing medium, e.g. water, is enough for LbL deposition by dip coating. The substrate, in Figure 10 a simple slide with positive surface charge, is dipped into the polyanion solution, washed to prevent cross-contamination of polycation with polyanion, dipped into the polycation solution and washed again (Figure 10 A). This cycle can be repeated as often as desired, but cross-contamination has to be considered after a certain number of cycles. With every coating step, more polyanion or polycation solution is carried into the water for washing. Furthermore, the PE concentrations do not stay constant since after washing some of the water will be also transferred to the PE solutions and dilute them [66]. The main principle behind the LbL deposition with PEs is based on electrostatic attraction between the charged surface and polyion or oppositely charged polyions, respectively. The adsorption of each PE layer causes a charge

overcompensation and allows for further layer adsorption of oppositely charged PEs. It also regulates the current layer thickness by repulsion of PEs of same charge and affects the stability of the dispersion [68, 69].

Figure 10: A) Schematic LbL deposition process with substrate slides and beakers; Steps 1 and 3 show the adsorption of polyions, in this case blue – polyanion and red – polycation by dipping the slide into a solution, 2 and 4 represent washing steps. B) First adsorption steps on the molecular level (simplified, idealised); Deposition started with a positively charged substrate, counter ions are not depicted. Taken from [67].

For nonplanar substrates, like colloidal particles, the LbL technique gives rise to other challenges. The use of PEs is well known in wastewater treatment as a flocculant. The coagulation-flocculation effect itself is highly dependent on the PE concentration and pH [70]. For non-ionic polymers, coagulation is induced via polymer bridging between the particles. For PEs in addition to bridging, mostly electrostatic interactions and charge neutralisation are responsible for that effect [71]. When aiming for layer deposition of PEs on the particles that should stay dispersed, the flocculation is something that must be prevented. The concentration of the flocculants, salt concentrations and the pH affect its performance [70]. Therefore, it is obvious, that the same parameters are relevant for the PE adsorption on colloids for layer

formation. PE and salt concentrations as well as salt type, solvent and adsorption time influence the formation and thickness of the PE layer and the stability of the particles in a dispersion [72–75].

Analysis of the PE multilayers revealed their amorphous nature which makes them less sensitive to the preparation process and individual defects in the layers. The adsorption of a PE layer on already existing layers differs from the adsorption to the rigid substrate surface. The alternating layers can interpenetrate each other and about one third of the PE layer charge is being compensated by this complexation. It is believed that the PE layers form in two steps, a fast adsorption of the PE layer to the already adsorbed layers and a slow rearrangement of the PE molecules. During this rearrangement, molecule segments diffuse into the underlying layers and allow for the complexation. The multilayers are thus “fuzzy” [67, 74, 75]. The morphology taken by the PE molecules themselves is dependent on the concentration and type of salt. High salt concentrations or multivalent ions screen the charges on the PE segments more which can then approach each other, forming loops. These loops cause the individual layers to be thicker and they protrude into the solvent. Low salt concentrations lead to elongated conformations due to repulsion and swelling of the PE chain and rather flat PE adsorption, thus thinner layers [69, 76].

Colloids can be coated by repeatedly dispersing them in PE solutions with centrifuging and washing steps in between, analogously to the dip coating described previously [75]. This is then called an immersive LbL assembly [77]. Complex composites can be achieved that way by the choice of different PEs and incorporated nanoparticles [78].

The LbL technique is also a method applicable for heterocoagulation by electrostatic interactions [79, 80]. In such case, NPs are deposited on larger core particles and can form a shell, giving the name *heterocoagulation*. Other possible causes for heterocoagulation are chemical reactivity between the core particle and the NP or hydrogen bonds. Size, shape, particle concentrations, surface charges of the particles involved as well as the surrounding medium and electrolytes affect the heterocoagulation, comparable to the layer deposition with PEs [79, 81]. Heterocoagulation can be supported by e.g. coupling agents or PE layers [80, 82].

Using iron oxide (Fe_3O_4) NPs, also called magnetite, magnetic properties can be introduced. Such composite particles are interesting for drug delivery, as they can be moved through the Fe_3O_4 NPs in a magnetic field to the target area [83]. Though drug delivery is a possible application for Ag patchy particles, the particles in this thesis were coated with Fe_3O_4 to inspect the LbL deposition of the positively charged PDADMAC layer.

3 Experimental Details

The experimental section provides an overview of the procedures which were used for the synthesis of silver patchy particles and their further functionalisation and processing. Unless stated otherwise for a specific sample, the procedures were carried out as described.

Samples were characterised as stated in section 3.2 with UV-Vis-NIR extinction spectroscopy and zeta potential measurements. Furthermore, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images were recorded of the particles and selected samples of coated particles were investigated with scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and optical microscopy.

A list of the chemicals and devices used for this work can be found in section 7.1 and 7.2 in the Appendix.

3.1 Experimental Procedure

This section covers the experimental procedures with all involved chemicals and the corresponding amounts used. Millipore water was used exclusively and will be referred to as just water. Absolute ethanol will be abbreviated as EtOH.

3.1.1 Synthesis of silver patches as templates

Silver patchy particles were synthesised according to the instructions in the Master's Thesis of Apostolos Kyrloglou [84]. The 10 mg mL^{-1} SiO_2 suspension stock used for synthesis was prepared at least one day prior to its first use by dispersing Merck Monospher[®] 500 with a particle size of 500 nm in water for one hour in an ultrasonic bath. The SiO_2 suspension was redispersed by rigorous shaking and additional ultrasonication for several minutes for the patch synthesis.

An oil bath was prepared and set to $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Water and the SiO_2 stock were mixed in a round bottom flask and heated under continuous stirring to $50 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using the oil bath. Once the desired temperature was reached, first aged silver nitrate (AgNO_3) solution (10 mM) and CH_2O solution (37%) were steadily added with a pipette. To assure

proper distribution of the added solutions, the mixture was stirred for 5 more minutes before continuously but rapidly adding the NH_3 solution (2.83 M). The end concentrations of all substances were held constant for any reaction volume with $0.084 \text{ mg mL}^{-1} \text{ SiO}_2$, 0.03 mM AgNO_3 , $80.6 \text{ mM CH}_2\text{O}$ and 17.0 mM NH_3 . Corresponding absolute volumes are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Absolute volumes of reaction components (in μL) during silver patch synthesis for different total reaction volumes (in mL). The respective concentrations stay constant.

Reaction volume (mL)	Water (mL)	SiO_2 (μL) 10 mg mL^{-1}	AgNO_3 (μL) 10 mM	CH_2O (μL) 37%	NH_3 (μL) 2.83 M
25	24.415	210	75	150	150
100	97.66	840	300	600	600
250	244.15	2100	750	1500	1500

A blue tint indicates that the reaction has finished. To remove unreacted components and to transfer the patchy particles to EtOH, the cooled down patchy particles were centrifuged and washed four times (4000 rcf, 10 min, 2 x water, 1 x EtOH with 50 % (v/v) in water, 1 x EtOH). Afterwards, the particles were transferred to fresh EtOH for the following functionalisation with DDT and to allow for longer storage compared to when water is used as a solvent. The volume of the sample in EtOH was 1/10 of the original reaction volume.

3.1.2 Functionalisation of silver patches with dodecanethiol

To functionalise the silver patches with DDT, the patchy particles in EtOH were first resuspended by shaking and ultrasonication. The particles were transferred to a round bottom flask and under continuous mixing with a magnetic stirrer, DDT was added in excess, i.e. $1.5 \mu\text{L}$ DDT per 1 mL patchy particle suspension. This is equivalent to approximately 6.3 mM DDT. The mixture was stirred for one more hour (h) at room temperature (RT) before centrifuging and washing three times with EtOH (4000 rcf, 5 min) and transferring to fresh EtOH.

3.1.3 Layer-by-layer coating of silica surface of patchy particles

The fact that silica shows a negative surface zeta potential [35] brought forth the idea to coat the bare silica sides of the already with DDT functionalised patchy particles with polyions. The main concept is to exploit the electrostatic attraction, using the LbL method, and repulsion by the nonpolar DDT. Particles were coated with one to three polyion layers by a procedure adapted from the doctoral thesis of R. N. Klupp Taylor [85].

3.1.3.1 First polyion layer: PDADMAC

For coating of silica and patchy particles with the polycation PDADMAC, a 1 wt% solution of PDADMAC containing 10 mM potassium nitrate (KNO_3) was prepared from a commercially available 20 wt% solution. Polyion solutions were freshly made for each experiment.

Functionalised patchy particles were then transferred from EtOH to water by centrifuging and washing with water once (4000 rcf, 5 min). The particles were redispersed in half the volume water of the initially centrifuged EtOH suspension volume. The washed and resuspended particles were then mixed in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio with the prepared 1 wt% PDADMAC solution by ultrasonication for 30 s. After another 2 min for the polyion to adsorb, the particles were centrifuged and washed three times with water (4000 rcf, 5 min) and redispersed in water.

3.1.3.2 Second polyion layer: PSS

Freshly made 1 wt% (i.e. 10 mg mL^{-1}) solution of PSS from PSS powder was used for the second polyion layer. Selected functionalised patchy particles, previously coated with the first PDADMAC-layer, were mixed in 1:1 (v/v) ratio with the prepared PSS solution. The adsorption and washing procedure was carried out analogously to the coating with PDADMAC.

3.1.3.3 Third polyion layer: PDADMAC

Selected patchy particles were coated with a third and final layer of PDADMAC. The layer was applied analogously to the first coating step.

3.1.4 Heterocoagulation with iron oxide

To verify the regioselective polyion adsorption, negatively charged Fe_3O_4 NPs were added and allowed to adsorb to the PDADMAC and later imaged using SEM.

Patchy particles with one PDADMAC layer were mixed for one minute in an ultrasonic bath with a concentrated Fe_3O_4 NP suspension which was previously made in the research group. To guarantee an excess of Fe_3O_4 NPs, 10 μL of concentrated Fe_3O_4 NPs were added for every millilitre of patchy particle suspension. After 30 min time to cover the patchy particles, the mixture was centrifuged and washed three times with water (4000 rcf, 5 min) and transferred to fresh water.

3.2 Characterisation methods

The principles of the characterisation methods in this thesis will be briefly explained. The devices that were used and their settings as well as the sample preparation are described.

3.2.1 UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy

UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy is a characterisation and quantification technique applied for a wide range of material types. Determination of e.g. particle concentrations in a dispersion is based on the Lambert-Beer law. The absorbance of the sample, which can be measured, is related to the concentration of the dispersed species, the extinction coefficient and the pathlength of the sample, e.g. in a cuvette [86].

Metal NPs can be characterised with UV-Vis-NIR spectroscopy to gain insight on their optical properties. The sample is measured in a spectrometer and illuminated with light of different wavelengths. The spectrometer contains two lamps, a deuterium and a tungsten-halogen lamp, to cover the UV and the visible region as well as part of the NIR. The monochromators in the spectrometer disperse the light from the lamps into its individual wavelengths so that the absorbance of specific wavelengths by the NPs can be determined. A double-beam spectrometer was used for this thesis to characterise the dispersed colloidal particles. In a double-beam device, the light beam is split into two before reaching the sample. The reference beam passes the cuvette

which contains the dispersion medium, and the sample beam passes the cuvette containing the dispersed sample. The refocused light beams then fall onto the detector [86, 87].

Depending on particle size, scattering from the particles must be considered. The measured signal then correlates to the overall extinction instead of pure absorbance.

The Ag patchy particles were measured in a Lambda 950 UV-Vis spectrometer from Perkin Elmer in a range of 300 to 1300 nm with an interval of 1 nm and with a scan speed of 277.37 nm per minute. Water and EtOH were used as solvent, which was also used as reference to eliminate the absorbance signals of the dispersant. Samples were measured in disposable UV-cuvettes semi-micro from BRAND with a pathlength of 10 mm. Samples were not diluted unless stated otherwise for specific spectra.

3.2.2 Zeta potential measurements

The zeta potential, as described in section 2.1.1, is mostly measured by electrophoresis which is an electrokinetic phenomenon. Charged particles move within an applied electric field. With that particle velocity, the electrophoretic mobility can be expressed, defined as the electrophoretic velocity per unit of applied electric field [23, 25]. In the Zetasizer used for the zeta potential measurements, the particle velocity or electrophoretic mobility, respectively, is measured by laser Doppler electrophoresis. A light beam crosses the sample capillary cell and is scattered by the particles moving within the applied field. The movement of the particles towards or away from the light source causes a Doppler effect, i.e. a phase shift of the wavelength of the beam. That beam is refocused with a reference beam and the velocities determined from the interferences [88]. It is thus possible to determine a velocity or electrophoretic mobility distribution instead of single values. Exploiting the relationship of the electrophoretic mobility and the zeta potential, the zeta potential distribution can be calculated via Henry's equation [20, 23, 25].

Zeta potential measurements were carried out in an aqueous solution. 995 μL of the aqueous sample were mixed with 5 μL of 0.2 M KNO_3 as a background electrolyte. This electrolyte affects κ^{-1} , i.e. the diffuse double layer thickness, and ensures a

reproducible measurement. The final sample containing 1 mM KNO_3 was then filled in a disposable capillary cell (Malvern Panalytical) with a syringe. The measurement was carried out in a Zetasizer NanoZS, also from Malvern Panalytical, at 20 °C with an equilibration time of 120 s. Five measurement runs with 5 s pause between each run were performed. The Smoluchowski model was selected for the measurements because of the polar and KNO_3 containing dispersant and the relatively large particles. The cell was cleaned by flushing with water and reused for further measurements.

3.2.3 Scanning electron microscopy

Structures in the nanometre range can be imaged with a SEM. The sample material is scanned in vacuum line for line by an electron beam in a SEM. The primary electrons interact with the atoms of the probe and their electron clouds. Backscattering of primary electrons, secondary electrons (SE), Auger electrons, X-ray emission and cathodoluminescence are the results of such interactions and are captured by detectors. An SE-detector which enables high resolution is the InLens. It is installed in the path of the primary electron beam above the probe. The InLens detector allows for SE detection at short working distances without significant loss of signal [89].

For sample preparation, 5 μl of the Ag patchy particle suspension was placed on a silicon wafer and dried at RT. The particles were imaged in a GeminiSEM 500 from ZEISS with an acceleration voltage of 10 kV for Ag patchy particles and 5 kV for particles covered with Fe_3O_4 NPs. The working distance was set between 3.0 and 5.0 nm. The InLens SE detector was used exclusively. Line integration and frame drift compensation were used with an iteration number of 6 during image capture.

3.2.4 Scanning transmission electron microscopy

STEM is a technique carried out on a transmission electron microscope. Like in SEM, electrons are accelerated in STEM towards the sample which is scanned by the resulting focused electron beam. The electrons interact with the atoms of the sample while passing through the sample and are scattered. The brightfield (BF) detector, located below the electron gun and the sample, detects electrons that leave the

sample at relatively small angles, which are smaller than the convergence angle of the incident beam. Darkfield (DF) detectors, or annular darkfield detectors, are ring detectors located outside of the optical axis and above the BF detector. They detect electrons scattered at angles that are larger than the convergence angle. High angle annular darkfield (HAADF) detectors collect electrons scattered at even larger angles than for DF [90, 91]. These are the main detectors which were also used to characterise the Ag patchy particles and allow for different contrasts, though other detectors also exist in STEM, e.g. for X-rays. The electrons are collected at the detectors and the signal intensities are amplified and visualised on a screen. The magnification of the STEM originates from the ratio of the sizes of the scanning area and the viewing screen [91]. For this work, only the images of the BF, DF4 and HAADF detectors are used to analyse the particles, as BF and DF2 yield similar contrasts (Figure 11).

Figure 11: STEM images of an exemplary Ag patchy particle with BF, DF2, DF4 and HAADF detectors. The Ag patch is dark for BF and DF2 as the electrons are scattered at higher angles and thus do not reach those detectors. In turn, DF4 and HAADF collect the electrons scattered at those angles and the Ag looks bright. BF and DF2 show similar contrast, however, the BF image shows sharper contours.

Two exemplary samples were prepared for STEM imaging. A holey carbon grid was placed on a 5 μ l drop of the sample suspension. The liquid was drawn through the grid with a tissue due to the capillary forces and the grids were let to dry. The samples were further prepared for STEM and kindly imaged by Dominik Drobek from the Institute of Micro- and Nanostructure Research in an FEI Titan Themis³ 300.

3.2.5 Optical microscopy

In an optical microscope, light is focused onto a plane in a sample. It can either pass the sample in a transmission microscope or be reflected. The light passes a system of lenses, which are the cause of the magnification, before reaching the detector, e.g. a

camera. The sample can be imaged in DF mode to enhance contrast. In BF, the sample is completely illuminated and the background is depicted white in images while the sample looks dark. For DF imaging, most light is held back by an aperture with only a ring-shaped orifice for the light to pass. The lens system collecting the light is equipped with a matching aperture ring that holds back the light that directly passes the orifice without being scattered on its way. Only light scattered from the structures in the sample passes the magnifying lenses and is detected, thus the structures look bright in the final image whereas the background is dark [92, 93].

Samples were imaged in a Nikon eclipse Ti transmission microscope and an Axio Imager Z.2 from ZEISS with an AxioCam 208 color. The Axio Imager Z.2 is compatible with the GeminiSEM 500 and allows for correlative microscopy.

The samples for the transmission microscope were prepared by spreading the dispersion on a glass slide (Carl Roth) and images were taken while the drop was not yet dried out. Images were recorded with the ThorCam software from ThorLabs. The image settings were adjusted to a gain of 1 x for minimum noise and by auto white balance before imaging, which was then turned off. A 20 x magnification was used. This was the highest magnification compatible with the DF mode needed for the investigation of particle assemblies.

The samples for the Axio were prepared analogously but were let to dry completely. The images and spectra were kindly recorded with the ZEN software at a magnification of 100 x in BF mode by Eric Görlitzer with an illumination time of 40.04 ms at maximum intensity. As the light is reflected from the sample, opaque slides like silicon wafers can also be used for sample preparation.

4 Results and discussion

The course and variation of the experiments in this thesis was highly dependent on the results of the single experiment steps and of iterative character. Therefore, the results will be mostly discussed in logical order for facilitated comprehension. The individual samples were assigned acronyms and a consecutive number. Ag patchy particle samples will be referred to as AgP, functionalised Ag patchy particles as AgPF and particles further coated with polyelectrolytes by the LbL technique will be abbreviated as AgPFPE. Particles coated with polyelectrolytes without former functionalisation will be referred to as AgPPE.

4.1 Silver patch synthesis

The synthesis of Ag patches was the first step to regioselective LbL coating of the SiO₂. The cup-like patches showed a specific UV-Vis-NIR spectrum. This is due to the nature of Ag nanostructures, which express LSPR. This spectrum was used as reference throughout all steps to track the integrity of the patches and thus ensure that only part of the SiO₂ stays bare for LbL coating. The preservation of Ag patches with their LSPR furthermore adds an extra function to the coated particles.

4.1.1 Reproduction of established patchy particle synthesis method

In general, the reproduction of the patch synthesis process (section 3.1.1) as template formation can be considered successful and sufficient for regioselective LbL coating. The distribution of patches and patch size was non-uniform, though. As shown in Figure 12, not all SiO₂ spheres have a patch and sizes differ from small dots to shells covering half the sphere. Nonetheless, the samples were sufficient for verifying the feasibility of regioselective coating with Ag patches as template. At the beginning of the study, large amounts of patchy particles were needed for testing different routes. Thus, a reaction volume of 250 mL was chosen for the batch synthesis. Due to the dropwise addition of the reactants and the large reaction volume, concentration gradients during synthesis and larger patch size distribution are to be expected. Even

for a 100 mL reaction volume, the uniformity of patch coverage does not change significantly (Figure 12 D). In any case, the necessity for quick production of enough patchy particles outweighed the need for uniform and controlled patch coverage, which is an issue to be addressed after establishing an effective LbL coating procedure. Furthermore, an option for large scale production of patchy particles with more uniform patch size could be the continuous patch synthesis using a T-mixer set-up as currently studied in our research group.

Figure 12: A) SEM image of sample AgP-3 from 250 mL reaction volume; B) Sample AgP-3 in round bottom flask, 250 mL reaction volume; C) SEM image of sample AgP-4 from 250 mL reaction volume; D) SEM image of sample AgP-13 from 100 mL reaction volume.

4.1.2 Transfer of patchy particles to EtOH for functionalisation

In Figure 13, the extinction spectrum of sample AgP-4 in two different media is depicted. The particles were synthesised in water as solvent and transferred to EtOH for storage and functionalisation.

Figure 13: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of sample AgP-4 in EtOH and in water normalised to 300 nm (left) and raw data (right) from 1 mL AgP-4 each.

The particles did not agglomerate in the new medium and the Ag patches stayed intact, as indicated by the blue colour of the dispersion. In fact, upon this transfer, the colour of the AgP-4 suspension became more vibrant. This subjective impression is confirmed by the UV-Vis-NIR spectra (Figure 13). The extinction in the red and NIR is higher for the EtOH sample, both qualitatively for the spectrum normalised to 300 nm and the raw data spectrum with additionally decreased extinction in the blue. In this case, the raw data can be compared as is, since the samples in EtOH and water originate from the same synthesis and thus have roughly the same concentration. The spectrum of AgP-4 in water also lies above the EtOH sample, thus showing a higher baseline of extinction in general (lowest at about 0.7 for water compared to approximately 0.45 for EtOH). This might explain why the sample at the same concentration in EtOH looked clearer than the one in water. SEM images of AgP-4 in EtOH confirm the intactness of the Ag patches. The signal values above 1 furthermore suggest that the concentration of the particle dispersion was too high especially for the sample dispersed in water.

As already observed by several research groups, amongst them Cai *et al.*, Yin *et al.* or Chen *et al.* [94–96], zerovalent Ag forms a silver oxide (Ag_2O) layer on its surface with the surrounding O_2 in air or water. Since the optical properties of Ag_2O differ from Ag, a red shift can be observed in the UV-Vis spectrum compared to elemental Ag and thus indicate such layer formation. Furthermore, this layer dissolves in water, releasing Ag^+ . Ag_2O on the surface is in equilibrium with the formed Ag^+ , which can

adsorb to the surface and prevent further dissolution of AgO_2 [97]. The formation of such a layer would partly explain the drastic change in the UV-Vis-NIR spectra in water as dispersant. The Ag patch surface can be oxidised and thus show different LSPR. In EtOH, on the other hand, the oxidation of Ag is unlikely. Ag clusters and nanostructures are currently studied as catalysts for EtOH oxidation which implies that EtOH is rather oxidised by Ag than the other way around [98–100]. Surely, the change of refractive index from water to EtOH also plays a role in the change of the LSPR. However, as the refractive index for water and EtOH differs only in the second decimal [101], this change should have a negligible effect compared to the formation of AgO_2 layer on the Ag. Spectra of AgP in EtOH or stored for several weeks or months cannot be compared directly with further processed particles (measured in water) because of this effect. This must be kept in mind not only for future analysis but also for the following processing of the AgP.

4.2 Functionalisation of silver patches with dodecanethiol

After the Ag patch synthesis by heterogeneous nucleation on the SiO_2 surface as described in 3.1.1, the patches were functionalised with DDT which bound to the silver via its thiol group. The effectivity of DDT functionalisation has been proven in the Master's thesis of Apostolos Kyrloglou [84]. The functionalisation procedure has been reproduced and fitting functionalisation conditions have been determined with subsequent LbL coating in mind.

4.2.1 Effect of dodecanethiol on patch integrity

AgPF were imaged with SEM and corresponding images confirmed that patches on SiO_2 were existent (Figure 43, Appendix). The patch morphology still resembled a cup-like shape with smooth edges. The integrity of Ag patches after DDT functionalisation is concluded from this observation. Apostolos Kyrloglou [84] has already shown the degradation of non-functionalised patchy particles over the course of time when stored in water or EtOH. Degradation was less prominent in particles dispersed in EtOH. The utilisation of DDT might show further stabilising effects, especially in combination with EtOH.

As evidence that DDT forms a protective layer, 500 μl of a 1 M potassium chloride (KCl) solution were added to 2 mL of AgP and AgPF in water (Figure 14). Upon introduction of chloride ions (Cl^-), the Ag^+ adsorbed to the Ag and AgO_2 surface of the unprotected patches can react with the Cl^- to silver chloride (AgCl) [102]. This reaction can be observed optically, as the Ag patches show LSPR and thus look coloured. The blue colour vanishes with Cl^- addition.

Figure 14: Samples AgP-2 (left vial) and AgPF-1 (right vial) before addition of 1 M KCl solution, immediately after addition of 1 M KCl solution, 7 h and three days after addition of 1 M KCl solution.

AgP-2 shows a slightly more vibrant blue than AgPF-1 before adding KCl (Figure 14, reference) but loses its colour immediately after mixing the samples with KCl solution (Figure 14 + KCl). Even after 7 h and after three days (Figure 14 + KCl 7 h and + KCl 3 d), the redispersed sample AgPF-1, the sample with DDT functionalisation, still shows a grey-blue tint whereas the unprotected sample AgP-2 looks white-grey and turbid. These findings are in accordance with the assumption, that thiols compete with Cl^- as the thiol group strongly binds to Ag via covalent bonds [102]. Furthermore, the initial DDT layer can form a passivating shell consisting of a mix of Ag_2S and chemisorbed DDT. Such a shell can prevent or at least slow down the degradation of Ag patches by inhibiting ion release and further oxidation [44, 48, 49]. This

hypothesis, however, needs further investigation which can be carried out similarly to the degradation study of non-functionalised particles of Apostolos Kyrloglou [84]. Therefore, differently synthesised AgPF could be kept in water, EtOH and dried and the patch integrity could be determined via SEM imaging.

4.2.2 Effect of dodecanethiol functionalisation conditions

The LSPR of metal NPs is dependent on the refractive index and dielectric constant of the surrounding medium, respectively [10]. It has also been reported that, among others, capping agents, adsorbed (mono-) layers and substrates in which the NPs could be embedded affect the LSPR as well [44]. With this in mind, UV-Vis-NIR measurements were carried out for AgPFs, which were functionalised in different manners to investigate if differences in the functionalisation procedure have an effect on LSPR and can thus be used to assess the DDT chemisorption as was done by e.g. Toh *et al.* [44].

All AgPFs were prepared from AgP-3 with a deviating procedure from section 3.1.2. AgPF-4 has been functionalised as described by Apostolos Kyrloglou [84] for 30 min at RT, AgPF-5 for 30 min at 50 °C and AgPF-6 has been functionalised overnight (24 h), also at RT. The spectra of the AgPFs, measured in EtOH, are shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of AgPF-4 (functionalised 30 min at RT), AgPF-5 (functionalised 30 min at 50 °C) and AgPF-6 (functionalised 24 h at RT) in EtOH normalised to 300 nm (left) and raw data (right).

It was found that a slight red shift of the observable peaks has occurred, which is more clearly visible in Figure 44 in the Appendix. The decrease in both extinction peaks in

the raw data spectra could be a result of particle losses during washing. However, for the data normalised to 300 nm, a decrease with higher temperature during functionalisation and even more with longer functionalisation time can be observed. The UV-peak at around 330 nm increases again for AgPF-6 compared to AgPF-5 (NIR peak as reference) and the graphs intersect in the raw data.

These results correspond to the expected change in resonance and to the results in the work of Toh *et al.* [44], who have studied 6-mercapto-1-hexanol (MH) interaction with Ag NPs. They observed a red shift of the UV-Vis spectrum with increasing exposure time of the NPs to MH, likely caused by the formation of a shell of chemisorbed MH. Increasing concentrations of MH added to the Ag NPs led to the same effect. However, times observed in their work ranged from 5 - 45 min with MH concentrations three orders of magnitude lower than the one used for DDT in this thesis [44]. For Au, the adsorption of alkanethiols such as DDT, has been studied by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy by Subramanian *et al.* [103]. It was revealed, that 80 – 85 % of the adsorption to the metal takes place within the first few seconds for a concentration of 1 mM. A full monolayer was achieved for an experiment time of approximately 53 min at 1 mM. The use of lower alkanethiol concentrations led to less coverage over the same experiment time [103]. Assuming, that the adsorption behaviour of alkanethiols to Ag is similar as for Au, the experimental procedure from the Master's thesis of Apostolos Kyrloglou [84] was altered to 1 h of functionalisation instead of 30 min in favour of a full monolayer formation. The decreasing extinction in the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum for longer functionalisation time (Figure 15), indicating the formation of an adsorbed layer or shell, supports this decision. The change in LSPR is connected to the newly introduced bonds between Ag and the thiol, thus reducing free valence electrons [9, 59]. Raising the DDT concentration instead of the functionalisation time could present an alternative to longer functionalisation time. As Subramanian *et al.* [103] have only mentioned adsorption during their work, it is furthermore of question, whether the alkanethiols constituting the observed monolayer were all chemisorbed to the Au surface and if a study of even longer functionalisation times may be necessary. The DDT layers could be investigated concerning chemisorption, coverage and monolayer properties e.g. how ordered or

dense it is. With such insight the current conditions of AgP functionalisation could be verified or perfected concerning exposure time and DDT concentration.

4.3 Coating with PDADMAC

The main aim of this present thesis was to selectively coat SiO₂ spheres with PE layers using Ag patches, which shield part of the SiO₂ surface, as a template. Particles with patchy polyion (multi-)layers and preferably persisting Ag NP optical properties were the desired result and aim. The coating with PDADMAC was tested for differing coating times. The particles were investigated by zeta potential measurements and SEM imaging as well as UV-Vis-NIR spectrometry to determine surface charges and the integrity of Ag patches.

4.3.1 Control coating – PDADMAC on bare silica

Before coating the AgPF, the feasibility of layer formation and charge reversal by polyions has been tested on bare SiO₂ spheres. The SiO₂ was coated with the LbL technique. Deviating from the later established coating procedure tailored to Ag patchy particles (section 3.1.3), 1 M KCl in the PDADMAC solution was used. A 2 wt% (i.e. 2 mg mL⁻¹) SiO₂ sol has been used to test the procedure with a coating time of 30 min. The measured zeta potential showed a charge reversal indicating the adsorption of the positively charged PDADMAC (Figure 16), the procedure was deemed effective and applied to the AgPF sample.

4.3.2 Coating of silver patchy particles - PDADMAC

After testing the LbL technique on bare SiO₂, 2 x 5 mL of functionalised patchy particle sample AgPF-1 were coated by the procedure described for the control coating (section 4.3.1), yielding samples AgPFPE-1 and AgPFPE-2.

The suspension of the washed particles seemed less vibrant in colour compared to the remaining AgPF-1. The zeta potential and UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the samples AgPF-1, AgPFPE-1 and AgPFPE-2 were measured and compared. The AgPFPE-1 spectrum is not analysable as the sample concentration and the signal was low

(Figure 45, Appendix). Thus, AgPFPE-1 will not be considered in the following evaluation.

Figure 16: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of sample AgPF-1 (functionalised) in EtOH and AgPFPE-2 (functionalised & coated) in water (left), normalised to 300 nm; zeta potential of bare SiO₂ particles (2 mg mL⁻¹), PDADMAC coated SiO₂ (2 mg mL⁻¹), sample AgPF-1 (functionalised AgP) and AgPFPE-2 (functionalised & coated AgP), unknown concentrations (right).

The differences in the spectra in Figure 16 are mainly due to the different solvents used (see section 4.1.2). The LSPR peaks visible in AgPF-1 are no longer present in AgPFPE-2. Except for a shoulder at around 330 nm, where a peak can be found for AgPF-1, the graph falls rather smoothly for AgPFPE-2 until approximately 800 nm and stays almost horizontal to the axis from there on. The behaviour of the spectrum beyond 1300 nm is unknown as this was the limit of the measurement in water. However, it cannot be ruled out that the graph would show a peak further in the IR as a slight increase in extinction seems to be setting in at approximately 1100 nm.

The zeta potential of AgPF-1 shown in Figure 16 is negative but with -44.9 ± 5.5 mV less negative than SiO₂, which is -62.7 ± 7.7 mV. The zeta potentials for AgPFPE-2 is positive with $+30.6 \pm 5.3$ mV and shows a charge reversal to AgPF-1. It lies below the zeta potential of PDADMAC coated silica without Ag patches ($+39.0 \pm 4.7$ mV).

At the time that the above measurements were made, it was not yet known, why the colour of the sample lost its intensity. The change of medium and resulting difference in spectra is depicted in Figure 13, but was discovered later in the course of experiments.

It was speculated that apart from particle losses during washing the Ag patches might have fallen off or were degraded due to some substance in the PDADMAC solution. SEM images revealed that the cup-like patches were still existent, but could not give an indication about the patch composition, i.e. if the patch was still composed of Ag (Figure 46, Appendix). Since the effect of Cl^- on bare Ag was known, the KCl addition to functionalised and non-functionalised patchy particles was compared as reference (see section 4.2.1, Figure 14) to treatment with PDADMAC solution. To further investigate the change in colour, a series of tests was set up. The coating time and KCl concentrations were varied to evaluate if a lower KCl concentration or shorter exposure time to a Cl^- containing solution had a positive effect of conserving the colour and give the same coating quality as the previously tested PDADMAC solution. The combinations of coating time and KCl concentrations are listed in Table 2. All samples were prepared from AgPF-3.

Table 2: Functionalised patchy particles coated with 1 wt% PDADMAC and varying KCl concentrations for 2 min and 10 min, respectively.

Sample	KCl concentration (M)	Coating time (min)
AgPFPE-3	1	10
AgPFPE-4	1	2
AgPFPE-5	0.01	2
AgPFPE-6	0.01	10

The samples were analysed in water with a UV-Vis-NIR spectrometer and with the zeta sizer. The UV-Vis-NIR spectra of these samples are compared to AgPFPE-2 in Figure 17. All samples had positive zeta potentials (Figure 18), indicating the charge reversal upon PDADMAC adsorption to AgPF-3.

The extinction spectra of all samples from Table 2 follow the same overall shape that can also be seen in Figure 16 for sample AgPFPE-2. This is visible in the spectra normalised to values between zero and one (Figure 18) and in the spectra, where the data is normalised to the values at 300 nm (Figure 17). Sample AgPFPE-2 is plotted there as reference. The main difference in the spectra in Figure 17 is the lower limit of extinction with AgPFPE-2 having the highest baseline at about 0.35. The samples

with 1 M KCl in the PDADMAC solution are second lowest, AgPFPE-3 with 10 min exposure time lying below AgPFPE-4 with only 2 min of exposure. A similar relation to coating time can be seen for AgPFPE-5 (2 min) and AgPFPE-6 (10 min) where the AgPFPE-6 spectrum lies below AgPFPE-5. The raw data also shows that the extinction in the UV region becomes lower with shorter coating time or lower KCl concentration, however, the individual concentrations of the samples are not known after the washing procedures after coating and particle losses could also affect the intensities so that small differences for the horizontal parts of the graphs (AgPFPE-3 vs. AgPFPE-4, AgPFPE-5 vs. AgPFPE-6) are insignificant in the raw data (Figure 47, Appendix).

Figure 17: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of samples AgPFPE-2 (1 M KCl, 30 min), AgPFPE-3 (1 M KCl, 10 min), AgPFPE-4 (1 M KCl, 2 min), AgPFPE-5 (10 mM KCl, 2 min) and AgPFPE-6 (10 mM KCl, 10 min), all measured in water and normalised to 300 nm.

The zeta potential reversals for all tested AgPFPEs (Figure 18) indicate, that shorter coating times and lower salt addition still yield satisfactory results. A sufficient amount of PDADMAC appears to be adsorbed fast enough to express a positive enough zeta potential even after 2 min of coating, so that the particles do not agglomerate after the adsorption process. This phenomenon is connected to the

overcompensation when polyions adsorb to the substrate layer and to the resulting repulsive forces between individual particles as mentioned in section 2.4 [69].

Figure 18: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of samples AgPFPE-2 (1 M KCl, 30 min), AgPFPE-3 (1 M KCl, 10 min), AgPFPE-4 (1 M KCl, 2 min), AgPFPE-5 (10 mM KCl, 2 min) and AgPFPE-6 (10 mM KCl, 10 min), all measured in water and normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum value as 1 (left); zeta potential of sample AgPF-3, AgPFPE-2, AgPFPE-3, AgPFPE-4, AgPFPE-5 and AgPFPE-6, unknown concentrations (right).

As observed by Bauer *et al.* [73], the salt concentration affects the charge reversal of uncoated to coated SiO₂ particles. At higher salt concentrations, the charge of individual PDADMAC chain segments is screened and the segments can move closer towards each other, effectively causing loops in the chain that can protrude from the SiO₂ surface. This would lead to more unoccupied surface to which more PDADMAC can then adsorb compared to the more elongated form of the polyelectrolyte in lower ionic strength environment. This in turn causes more positive charges to adsorb to the SiO₂ and yield higher charge density [73]. As a reference, Bauer *et al.* [73] classified very high salt concentrations for sodium chloride beginning with 0.1 M and a concentration of 10 mM was studied in the context of low ionic strength.

In Figure 18, the difference in zeta potential between the coated particles with 1 M KCl containing PDADMAC solution (AgPFPE-3 and AgPFPE-4) and with 10 mM KCl containing solution (AgPFPE-5 and AgPFPE-6) is about 5 mV. As all samples showed a charge reversal and none of the samples agglomerated, all resulting zeta potentials were high enough to stabilise the particles electrostatically and the lower salt concentration was selected for further coating experiments. Furthermore, the ions at high salt concentrations can also screen the negatively charged SiO₂ surface and

reduce the adsorption of PDADMAC by electrostatic forces which makes other interactions all the more important. To enhance the hydrophobic interactions of the polymer chains at high salt concentrations, higher temperatures might be needed during coating [75]. To keep the coating procedure as simple as possible, a lower salt concentration of 10 mM was chosen, with which similar zeta potentials to 1 M KCl can be achieved. As the final aim was to produce multilayers, exposing the Ag patch to Cl⁻ ions again and again seemed to risky and thus KCl was replaced by KNO₃, though Cl⁻ ions remain in the PDADMAC solution.

Even though the graph shapes do not change significantly and the LSPR peaks of the AgP and AgPF samples cannot be reproduced, the reduction of coating time without more negative effects is of benefit, especially with potential continuous flow coating in mind for the future. The coating time was thus reduced to 2 min for all following AgPFPE samples as described in 3.1.3.1. A comparison for a coating time of 2 min between PDADMAC solution with 10 mM KCl and 10 mM KNO₃ is shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of sample AgPFPE-5 (PDADMAC coating with 10 mM KCl) and AgPFPE-7 (PDADMAC coating with 10 mM KNO₃) for a coating time of 2 min, all measured in water and normalised to 300 nm (left); zeta potentials of sample AgPF-3, AgPFPE-5 and AgPFPE-7 (right).

The sample coated with PDADMAC solution containing KCl (AgPFPE-5) shows lower extinction signal than sample AgPFPE-7, which was coated with PDADMAC solution containing KNO₃. The spectrum of AgPFPE-7 distinctly rises again in the NIR region and shows a blue shift compared to AgPFPE-5 in the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum normalised to values between zero and one (Figure 48, Appendix). The zeta potential of AgPFPE-7, also prepared by coating AgPF-3, is more positive than the zeta potential

of AgPFPE-5. The coating with the solution containing KNO_3 led to higher overcompensation which implies, that more PDADMAC has been adsorbed to the particles.

For proper comparison of the AgPF and AgPFPE, new samples of particles coated with PDADMAC were measured in EtOH. AgPFPE-13 a) are patchy particles coated with a PDADMAC solution with 10 mM KNO_3 , AgPFPE-13 b) with 10 mM KCl. The coating time was 2 min in each case. Aliquots from both variations were transferred to EtOH and the UV-Vis-NIR spectra of these samples were measured in water and in EtOH. AgPF-8 was measured exclusively in EtOH. The samples AgPFPE-13 a) and b) in the UV-Vis-NIR spectra in Figure 20 are compared to their “precursor” AgPF-8.

Figure 20: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of sample AgPFPE-13 before (AgPF-8) and after coating with PDADMAC with 10 mM KNO_3 (AgPFPE-13 a) and 10 mM KCl (AgPFPE-13 b) normalised to 300 nm (top left); Zeta potential of AgPF-8, AgPFPE-13 a and b (top right). UV-Vis-NIR spectra of sample AgPFPE-13 before (AgPF-8) and after coating with PDADMAC with 10 mM KNO_3 (AgPFPE-13 a) and 10 mM KCl (AgPFPE-13 b) normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum value as 1 (bottom left); raw data of AgPFPE-13 a and b (bottom right). UV-Vis-NIR spectra of all samples were measured in water and EtOH.

The zeta potential is reversed from -54.9 ± 6.8 mV for AgPF-8 to $+62.8 \pm 7.1$ mV and $+66.1 \pm 7.9$ mV for AgPFPE-13 a and b, respectively (Figure 20 (top right)). In both cases, whether coated in a KCl or KNO_3 containing solution, the spectra of samples in EtOH express a peak around 330 nm, though the peak is not as high as for AgPF-8 (Figure 20 (top left)). The extinction in the red and NIR increases again with transfer from water to EtOH. Compared to the samples in water with the shoulder at 330 nm and rather flat curve in the NIR, the spectrum from in EtOH dispersed samples resemble the initial spectrum of patchy particles better. Therefore, the effect must be reversible at least to some extent.

The raw data and data normalised between zero and one (Figure 20 (bottom right and bottom left)), allow further insight on the differences in optical properties. The resemblance of the AgPF-8 spectrum and the coated particles transferred back to EtOH is even more prominent. The signal is highest in the infrared for particles dispersed in EtOH, for normalised and for raw data alike. It is highest in the UV for samples measured in water. The bottom left spectra of Figure 20 show that the peak in the UV is located at lower intensities for AgPF-8 with the signal in the IR as a reference value. The intensity of the peak increases and a red shift is visible from AgPF-8 to AgPFPE-13 a (in EtOH) to AgPFPE-13 b (in EtOH).

Either the DDT layer on the patchy particles is not a full and ordered monolayer and free Ag surface can still react with water or the conformation of the DDT layer covering the Ag patch varies between water and EtOH dispersed particles. DDT-water and DDT-EtOH interaction is expected to vary as DDT is hydrophobic. This, in turn, influences the immediate environment of the Ag patch and thus the LSPR [9, 59]. Furthermore, the solvent effects of EtOH on PDADMAC could be investigated to find out more about the PE-layer conformation on the patchy particles in EtOH. The coating of Ag patchy particles with PDADMAC and 10 mM KNO_3 in general is feasible and effective as the zeta potential reversals indicate. The PDADMAC itself shows a general compatibility with the patchy particles.

4.3.3 Regioselectivity of PDADMAC coating

In order to prove, whether the coating with PDADMAC was regioselective, AgPFPE particles were mixed with Fe_3O_4 NPs as described in section 3.1.4. As the used Fe_3O_4 NPs are negatively charged, they attach to the positively charged PDADMAC due to electrostatic attraction (section 2.4). Such composite particles will be referred to as AgPFPE – Fe_3O_4 . The Fe_3O_4 NPs are visible in the SEM and STEM and thus areas covered in Fe_3O_4 can be distinguished from Fe_3O_4 – free surfaces. A comparison of functionalised patchy particles before and after coating with PDADMAC and Fe_3O_4 NPs can be found in Figure 21. STEM images of exemplary AgPFPE-14 – Fe_3O_4 particles are shown in Figure 22.

Figure 21: Comparison of Fe_3O_4 – free SiO_2 (A) and Fe_3O_4 covered SiO_2 (B); A) SEM image of sample AgPF-8, 50 k magnification, 10 kV; B) SEM image of sample AgPFPE-14- Fe_3O_4 , 50 k magnification, 5 kV. Sample AgPFPE-14 was made by coating AgPF-8 with PDADMAC.

The SiO₂ surface of the particles in the SEM image of the AgPF-8 sample (Figure 21 A) is smooth compared to the uneven surface of AgPFPE-14 (Figure 21 B), indicating that those particles are successfully covered in Fe₃O₄ NPs. The Ag patches, which are partly detached in sample AgPFPE-14 – Fe₃O₄, show a similar surface texture as from AgPF-8. As a conclusion, the Ag patches are free of Fe₃O₄ NPs and consequently not coated with PDADMAC.

The STEM images in Figure 22 and Figure 23 show selected particles from sample AgPFPE-14 – Fe₃O₄. The individual images were taken with different detectors simultaneously resulting in BF (A), DF (B) and in HAADF (C) mode images. The exemplary BF image in Figure 22 is enlarged. That way, the Fe₃O₄ NPs are more clearly discernible. The images for BF, DF and HAADF have the same sizes in Figure 23 and provide further examples of patchy particles covered with Fe₃O₄.

Figure 22: STEM images of sample AgPFPE-14- Fe₃O₄. A) BF; B) DF, DF4 detector; C) HAADF. Scale bar corresponds to 200 nm, 130 k magnification.

Figure 23: Collection of STEM images of sample AgPFPE-14-Fe₃O₄. A) BF; B) DF, DF4 detector; C) HAADF. Scale bar corresponds to 200 nm, 130 k magnification.

Generally, the Ag scatters electrons to higher angles and therefore the patches look dark in the BF (little to no intensity) and white in the DF and HAADF (high intensity). Fe_3O_4 NPs are best visible in the DF mode. The Ag patches in all images (Figure 22 and Figure 23) consist of several individual spots which constitute the whole patch. This suggests polycrystallinity of the Ag patch as was already noted in a previous work in the research group [84]. These individual Ag grains can be discerned by their parallel lines within a grain, albeit not parallel to the lines of adjacent grains (Figure 24).

Figure 24: BF STEM image of a fallen off Ag patch. The individual grains and holes in the patch are visible. The scale bar corresponds to 200 nm.

Dots, which are smaller than the individual Ag spots forming the Ag patch, cover the rest of the SiO_2 . These dots, the Fe_3O_4 NPs, cause a fuzzy appearance of the SiO_2 sphere. In the BF (A) and DF (B), the Fe_3O_4 are especially visible at the borders of the particle cross sections. The Fe_3O_4 are less prominently visible in the HAADF (C). Such a fuzzy layer is also visible on the Ag patch in Figure 23 (A1 and B1). The layer with Fe_3O_4 NPs is thin and discontinuous. In Figure 22 and Figure 23 (A2-C2) the Ag patches show an even border without an indication of Fe_3O_4 NPs adsorbed to the Ag. Differently sized holes are visible in the Ag patches in the HAADF images. Those holes either face towards the detector or away from it. It is not visible, if PDADMAC and thus Fe_3O_4 NPs are adsorbed to that confined SiO_2 area or the SiO_2 surface on the opposite side of the particle. Nonetheless, such holes can explain the Fe_3O_4 NPs presumably attached to the Ag patch in Figure 23 (A1-C1). The hole might be located perpendicular to the

imaging plane and superimposed by the Ag signal. This theory matches the irregular distribution of Fe_3O_4 NPs on the Ag patch in B1.

Figure 25: A) Sample AgPFPE-14- Fe_3O_4 with a commercial magnet taped to the eppi. The particles are visible as a grey shadow close to the magnet; B) Particles accumulated at the eppi wall after removal of the magnet.

These findings prove that the coating of the AgPF with PDADMAC is regioselective. While the SiO_2 surface is covered completely in Fe_3O_4 NPs, which implies that PDADMAC adsorbed successfully to all SiO_2 , the Ag patches are mostly bare. Local fuzzy regions on the Ag patch are likely caused by holes in that patch, exposing SiO_2 for PDADMAC adsorption. The patchy particles show magnetic properties after heterocoagulation with Fe_3O_4 . They are attracted by a commercial magnet and move through the solvent in its magnetic field (Figure 25). This regioselective introduction of magnetic properties via Fe_3O_4 is a promising method for multifunctional patchy particles for possible future research.

4.4 Effect of polyelectrolyte multilayers on regioselectivity

Single layer formation was compared to multilayers with alternating PDADMAC and PSS coating. According to Matsumoto *et al.* [83] and Caruso *et al.* [80], multilayers of PEs lead to a more even distribution of Fe_3O_4 NPs during heterocoagulation. The zeta potential of particles with a single PE layer and with three layers will be compared as well as SEM images of their Fe_3O_4 NP coated counterparts. Particles with two PE layers will be abbreviated AgPFPE2, particles with three layers are referred to as AgPFPE3.

4.4.1 Control coating- PSS on PDADMAC/Silica and PSS on PDADMAC/AgP

For the second PE layer, PSS was used. The first attempt of coating with PSS was analogously to PDADMAC coating with addition of KNO_3 (10 mM) to the PSS solution. Sample AgPFPE-8 was coated with PSS, yielding sample AgPFPE2-1. The zeta potentials of those samples are depicted in Figure 26.

Figure 26: Zeta potentials of sample AgPFPE-8 (PDADMAC), AgPFPE2-1 (PSS/PDADMAC with KNO_3), SiO_2 coated with PDADMAC and with PSS/PDADMAC without KNO_3 .

The zeta potential of AgPFPE2-1 does not show a charge reversal. The zeta potential, however, is less positive than for AgPFPE-8. PDADMAC coated SiO_2 was treated with a PSS solution without any additional salts for control coating to investigate the still positive zeta potential of AgPFPE2-1. The zeta potential of PDADMAC/ SiO_2 undergoes a charge reversal upon coating with PSS. Based on these findings, the second LbL coating step with PSS was carried out without further salt addition to the PSS solution.

4.4.2 PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC

Samples AgPFPE-11, AgPFPE2-3 and AgPFPE3 were made by coating sample AgPF-7 with one, two or three layers of PE, respectively. The particles were subsequently coated with alternating layers of PDADMAC and PSS as described in section 3.1.3 and analysed after each step. The UV-Vis-NIR spectra and zeta potentials of those samples can be found in Figure 27.

Figure 27: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of particles before coating (AgPF-7) in EtOH, sample AgPFPE-11 (PDADMAC), AgPFPE2-3 (PSS/PDADMAC) and sample AgPFPE3 (PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC) in water normalised to 300 nm (right); zeta potentials of AgPFPE-11, AgPFPE2-3 and AgPFPE3 (left).

The normalised UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the coated particles have approximately the same shape. There is a shoulder instead of the peak at around 350 nm, which is visible in the spectrum of AgPF-7. The extinction in the IR is low for all coated particles AgPFPE-11, AgPFPE2-3 and AgPFPE3 compared to AgPF-7. The coating with PSS and a second PDADMAC layer does not significantly affect the optical properties of the Ag patches. The zeta potential for AgPFPE-11, which has a single layer PDADMAC, is positive, becomes negative after coating with PSS and again positive with the second PDADMAC layer. The zeta potentials of a single PDADMAC layer with $+48.7 \pm 5.5$ mV and three layers, a second PDADMAC layer as the outer layer, with $+58.7 \pm 6.8$ mV have a difference of approximately 10.0 mV. The particles coated with three PE layers have a higher positive potential than with just one layer, though the difference is less than twice the standard deviation. This zeta potential reversal indicates that the formation of the second and third PE layer was successful.

As the zeta potentials of single and multilayer coatings are in a similar range, both samples were coated with Fe_3O_4 NPs to gain further insight about the PE layers. The SEM images of $\text{AgPFPE-11-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ and $\text{AgPFPE3-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ are shown in Figure 28 and the Fe_3O_4 NP distribution on the particles are compared.

Figure 28: A) Single layer sample $\text{AgPFPE-11-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$; B) Multilayer sample $\text{AgPFPE3-1-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ with details of damaged Ag patches (red boxes). 25 k magnification, 5 kV.

The particles in sample $\text{AgPFPE-11-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ (Figure 28 A) are covered non-uniformly in Fe_3O_4 NPs. The Ag patches show no adsorbed Fe_3O_4 . Sample $\text{AgPFPE3-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ (Figure 28 B) is comparable to $\text{AgPFPE-11-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ in Fe_3O_4 NP coverage. Patches have partly fallen off in both samples. Patches with uneven edges can be found in sample $\text{AgPFPE-11-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ as well as for $\text{AgPFPE3-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, but damaged patches are more prominent in $\text{AgPFPE3-Fe}_3\text{O}_4$. Those patches do not form a whole patch anymore and constitute of several Ag dots (Figure 28 B, enlarged red boxes).

The change in patch shape is visible when comparing the multilayer coated particles with freshly synthesised or functionalised AgP. As the PEs themselves do not cause direct harm to the Ag patches, the coating procedure was investigated for any damaging effects. During washing, the particles are resuspended by ultrasonication. With every cycle of PE coating, at least four additional resuspension steps (3 x wash,

1 x resuspend in fresh solvent) of varying time are carried out. Particles were sonicated until fully resuspended. The effect of prolonged ultrasonication was determined as a possible degradation factor. To verify this, non-functionalised AgP-3 in EtOH were kept in an ultrasonication bath and 1 mL of the sample was taken after 5 min, 10 min, 30 min and after 60 min. SEM images were taken of the particles at those different times and can be found in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Sample AgP-3 from EtOH before ultrasonication and after 5, 10, 30 and 60 min of ultrasonication. Degraded AgP-1 after one week in air as comparison. The scale bar corresponds to 500 nm, 25 k magnification, 10 kV.

The Ag patches (Figure 29) before ultrasonication treatment show smooth edges. After 5 min of ultrasonication, the edges become uneven and the patches are not continuous. The patch surface looks bumpy, but not rough. The patches after 10, 30 and 60 min look similar to the ones after 5 min except patches consist more prominently of a centre patch residue and surrounding dots of Ag. Some patches remain intact, indicating that patches are not damaged uniformly throughout the sample. The main damage is done within the first 5 min which explains the almost identical looking UV-Vis-NIR spectra of the coated particles with one to three PE layers. Though the particles were ultrasonicated more often for multilayers, the

damage does not progress with longer ultrasonication. The patches of sample AgP-1, stored for 1 week on a silica wafer in air, show a rough surface and ridged structures. The degraded patches' appearance is different from the patches exposed to prolonged ultrasonication. It can be assumed that the patches are damaged during repeated sonication rather than degraded. It must further be investigated whether that stress and consequent damage on the patches is caused by the ultrasonication itself, the heat generation during that process or both. Furthermore, a difference in repeated sonication for shorter times of e.g. 5 min and permanent ultrasonication for longer times, e.g. 60 min, may exist.

It has been proven that the PE multilayers consisting of three layers are feasible without loss of optical properties compared to a single PE layer. The zeta potential for particles with three layers is comparable to the zeta potential after coating with one PE layer. No difference was determined for Fe_3O_4 NP adsorption between one or three layers. It was stated that three intercalating PE layers of PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC were necessary to homogeneously coat polystyrene (PS) particles with Fe_3O_4 NPs, alternating Fe_3O_4 NP layers and PEs [80]. The observations were made on particles with several Fe_3O_4 layers [80], which could explain why in this current work no difference between single and multilayers was visible. This effect of improved homogeneity is likely influenced by the number of PE layers between Fe_3O_4 layers as well as the number of Fe_3O_4 NP layers. As no significant improvement was gained by multilayers, experiments were further carried out with single PDADMAC layers. The number of washing steps and redispersions in an ultrasonication bath was reduced that way. This strategy allowed for more throughput and less particle losses during washing steps without any evident disadvantages. For further approaches with Fe_3O_4 NPs to introduce magnetic properties to the patchy particles, multilayers with alternating PEs and Fe_3O_4 are suggested.

4.5 Tuning of regioselective coating size

Patch size and distribution is not uniform. Aiming for a higher patch yield and smaller size distribution, the patch synthesis was adapted. As a result, the free surface presented by the particles for PE coating is affected. The synthesis from section 3.1.1

was altered in reaction volume and SiO₂ concentration (Table 3). The AgNO₃ to NH₃ ratio and their individual concentrations were kept constant.

Table 3: Modified SiO₂ concentration and reaction volume in Ag patch synthesis with reference to corresponding SEM images in Figure 30.

Sample	SiO ₂ concentration (mg mL ⁻¹)	Reaction volume (mL)
AgP-5 (A)	0.05	25
AgP-6 (B)	0.02	25
AgP-14 (C)	0.02	200

SEM images of the AgPs from the modified patch synthesis and the corresponding UV-Vis-NIR spectra normalised to 300 nm can be found in Figure 30.

Figure 30: A) SEM image of sample AgP-5 (0.05 mg mL⁻¹ SiO₂, reaction volume: 25 mL); B) SEM image of sample AgP-6 (0.02 mg mL⁻¹ SiO₂, reaction volume: 25 mL); C) SEM image of sample AgP-14 (0.02 mg mL⁻¹ SiO₂, reaction volume: 200 mL); UV-Vis-NIR spectra of samples AgP-4 (original), AgP-5, AgP-6 and diluted sample AgP-14 (bottom right).

The Ag patches of sample AgP-5 are overall larger than for the previously used SiO₂ concentration of 0.084 mg mL⁻¹. Not all SiO₂ spheres have a patch or the patch might face downwards. While the Ag patches still have a cup-like appearance, the edges are rougher and show dendritic character. Sample AgP-6 has a higher Ag patch yield than AgP-5 with mostly similar patch size. One to three patches can be found on one SiO₂ sphere. As in AgP-5, the patches become dendritic at the edges but maintain an overall cup-like shape. Ag NPs can be found amongst the patchy particles, indicating homogenous nucleation of Ag. Sample AgP-14 virtually has no SiO₂ spheres without a patch, but the patch size distribution is broad with patch sizes ranging from dots to half spheres, forming Janus particles.

The corresponding extinction spectra all show higher extinction values in the NIR than the sample AgP-4, which was synthesised using the original SiO₂ concentrations and reaction volume of 0.084 mg mL⁻¹ and 250 mL, respectively. All spectra of the modified samples are blue-shifted and show higher extinction in the visible region compared to AgP-4, especially in the red. AgP-5 and AgP-6 extinction values rise step wise compared to the rather constantly rising AgP-4 spectrum. The sharp peak at 330 nm corresponds to the out-of-plane quadrupole SPR of the Ag patches and is present in all spectra [16]. The patch morphology and the shapes of the spectra of AgP-5 and AgP-6 are reminiscent of the patches synthesised with 5 mM NH₃ from Sadafi *et al.* [16]. In their electronic supplementary information, further SEM images and extinction spectra were shown of particles in a similar size range as used for this work, i.e. 290 nm and 530 nm SiO₂ spheres. It is possible that the spectra of AgP-5 and AgP-6 show that shift and change in shape due to the influence of the flower-like shape on the LSPR. This morphology is likely a result of the use of aged NH₃ solution during synthesis of AgP-5 and AgP-6, changing the effective NH₃ concentration. For AgP-14, a freshly made NH₃ solution was used, yielding smooth or rippled but not dendritic edges. The broad extinction peak in the NIR is caused by in-plane dipole LSPR [16]. This broad peak of AgP-14 deviates from the AgP-4 spectrum, likely because of the differing patch size distribution and several patches located on one SiO₂ sphere. Those patches may be located on opposite sides of the SiO₂, in the vicinity of each other or even touching. This could cause coupling between the individual patch resonances, comparable to the coupling of dendritic structures within a patch

[16]. Figure 50 in the Appendix shows a photograph of the dispersions of AgP-14 and AgPF-8, which was made from AgP-4. In this photograph, the difference in extinction spectra and therefore colour intensity at roughly the same particle concentration is visible macroscopically.

With the presumption that all AgNO_3 reacts to elemental Ag and deposits on the SiO_2 spheres with 10 nm patch thickness, the coverage was estimated. 6 % of the total SiO_2 surface must be covered in Ag after patch synthesis with 0.084 mg mL^{-1} SiO_2 of 500 nm size. When using only 0.02 mg mL^{-1} SiO_2 , 27 % of the total surface is covered. This estimate is in accordance with the SEM images that show more and larger Ag patches for samples with lower SiO_2 concentration during synthesis. The calculation can be found in section 7.3.1 of the Appendix, the nanosphere curvature was neglected.

The patch size and consequently regioselective coating area can be successfully tuned by altering the available SiO_2 surface for heterogenous nucleation by changing the SiO_2 concentration during synthesis. More uniform patch sizes can be achieved in smaller reaction volumes due to better mixing. A continuous flow set-up presents a promising alternative to this batch approach. Ag patchy particle samples with high yield and more uniform patch size, preferably close to half spheres, are best suited for self-organisation studies (section 4.7). Only few bare SiO_2 spheres can interfere during the self-organisation and the individual particles show less diverse properties, e.g. interacting surface area.

4.6 Evaluation of dodecanethiol functionalisation and its necessity

With the results from section 4.2, it is obvious, that DDT functionalisation can prevent further oxidation of the Ag patch. The question remains, nonetheless, if DDT repels the polyions used for coating as DDT shows hydrophobic properties while polyions are water soluble and hydrophilic. In this section, the necessity of that time-consuming functionalisation step will be evaluated. The effect of DDT on the patchy particles as a potential protective layer and “repellent” of polyions is investigated.

4.6.1 Role of dodecanethiol during coating with PDADMAC

In order to establish if functionalising the Ag patches with DDT is necessary, Ag patchy particles *before* and *after* DDT functionalisation were treated with PDADMAC as explained in 3.1.3 and compared with each other. Visualisation of the location of PDADMAC was achieved by heterocoagulation with Fe_3O_4 NPs as described in section 3.1.4. The results are shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: A) Sample AgP-13 (eppi, blue liquid) before addition of PDADMAC and sample AgPPE-16 in 1 wt% PDADMAC (glass vial, grey liquid); B) SEM image of AgP-13, 25 k magnification, 10 kV; C) SEM image of AgPPE-16, 25 k magnification, 10 kV; D) SEM image of AgPPE-16- Fe_3O_4 , 50 k magnification, 5 kV.

Upon addition of PDADMAC solution to the patchy particle sample AgP-13 without DDT, skipping particle transfer to ethanol and back to water, the mixture turned from a light blue to a turbid grey within seconds (sample AgPPE-16) as depicted in Figure 31 A. The spectrum of AgPPE-16 was not measured as the difference was clearly visible by eye and the sample was immediately processed further with Fe_3O_4 for SEM imaging (sample AgPPE-16- Fe_3O_4).

Cup-like, smooth Ag patches on SiO₂ spheres are visible in Figure 31 B. The particles visible in Figure 31 C and D show the residues of those Ag patches which are mostly detached from the SiO₂ and have lost their cup shape. The coated areas with PDADMAC, indicated by the Fe₃O₄ NPs that make the surface of the sphere look rough, seem to be non-uniform among different particles, but cover SiO₂ and patch residues alike.

The formerly produced and functionalised samples AgPFPE-2 and AgPFPE-12 will be used as examples to determine the effect of DDT. In comparison to AgPPE-16 (Figure 31), the colour of sample AgPFPE-2 in Figure 32 A still gives off a blue hue despite PDADMAC addition to its “precursor” AgPF-1. While the colour does not look as saturated after washing the sample and replacing the PDADMAC solution with water (Figure 32 A right image), this can also be accounted for by particle and Ag patch losses during the washing procedure, which effectively causes the sample to be more dilute than before and thus look less colourful. Figure 32 B and C show SEM images of AgPPE-12 before and after heterocoagulation with Fe₃O₄ NPs. The patches retain their cup-like shape and do not seem to be covered with Fe₃O₄ NPs, indicating that PDADMAC does not adsorb to the functionalised Ag patches.

Figure 32: A) Sample AgPFPE-2 mixed with 1 wt% PDADMAC and 1 M KCl (left) and after centrifugation and washing (right), the blue tint is still visible; B) SEM image of sample AgPFPE-12, 50 k magnification, 10 kV; C) SEM image of AgPFPE-12-Fe₃O₄, 25 k magnification, 5 kV.

The reason for the degradation of non-functionalised patches upon addition of PDADMAC is likely a reaction of the unprotected patch with the Cl^- in the PDADMAC solution. By mixing the AgP with the PDADMAC solution, with Cl^- as counterions to the polycations, the Ag^+ can react with the Cl^- to form AgCl as already described in section 4.2.1. According to Levard *et al.*, the Cl/Ag ratio affects the formation of either AgCl precipitates or soluble, negatively charged AgCl_x species. A relatively low ratio of $\text{Cl}/\text{Ag} \leq 535$ leads to AgCl precipitation. The AgCl adsorbs to the Ag NP surface and builds a AgCl layer on the NP [102]. Li *et al.* [104] have also observed the coagulation of Ag NPs promoted by the formation of such AgCl layers after mixing with sodium chloride and their provided TEM images of said coagulated particles are reminiscent of the Ag patch residues after KCl or PDADMAC addition (Figure 33). This similarity indicates that the patches also degraded with the formation of AgCl due to PDADMAC.

Figure 33: A) SEM image of sample AgPPE-16, 25 k magnification, 10 kV; B) SEM image of sample AgP-4 and KCl mixture, 25 k magnification, 10 kV.

With a 1 wt% PDADMAC solution of low molecular weight of 100000-200000 Da and thus approximately a molar mass of 100000-200000 g mol^{-1} , the estimated concentration of Cl^- during particle coating is 3 mM (section 7.3.2 in the Appendix) and falls into the category of low Cl/Ag ratio, supporting the theory, that the structures found on the SiO_2 spheres in Figure 33 are indeed AgCl. These findings make the protection of the Ag or the use of another polycation without oxidising counterions obligatory in order to not damage the Ag patch template.

It is shown that DDT builds such a protective layer. The still intact functionalised patches have already been shown in Figure 32, where PDADMAC addition did not cause the prominent transformation in patch form under the influence of Cl^- .

The exact mechanism of preventing further Ag dissolution and reaction to AgCl has not yet been determined in our case of Ag patches on SiO₂, but the theory of the formation of a chemisorbed DDT monolayer passivating the Ag patch seems most probable as was already discussed in section 4.2.1 [44, 103]. This layer, however, does not protect the patch from degradation over a long period of time, but prevents it in the short term. This is shown in Figure 14 in section 4.2.1, where the colour slowly turns to grey and the dispersion becomes more turbid over time.

As PDADMAC is only commercially available with Cl⁻ as a counterion, it is not possible to show whether it would coat the bare Ag patch without any further treatment of the PDADMAC solution by e.g. ion exchange. However, reports of negative zeta potential for Ag NPs indicate, that PDADMAC would also cover the Ag patch if it were to remain stable [102]. This leads to the conclusion, that the above-mentioned effect also prevents the Ag patch from being coated with PDADMAC as is visible in Figure 32 C. DDT seems to efficiently work as either a spacer, keeping the PDADMAC far enough away so that electrostatic attraction does not take any effect or even repel the polyion due to its hydrophobicity. In any case, if the LbL technique is to be carried out with PDADMAC, a functionalisation with an organothiols such as DDT proves itself essential.

4.6.2 Role of dodecanethiol during coating with PEI

Testing the shielding properties of DDT for other polyions, the AgP and AgPF were coated with poly(ethylene imine) (PEI), a polyelectrolyte that carries charges at its amine groups depending on pH and which contains no Cl⁻. The particles were coated for 30 min with 1 wt% PEI similarly to the coating with PDADMAC as described in section 3.1.3 except no KNO₃ was added to the solution and the particles were sonicated for 1 min instead of 30 s. The pH of the solution was determined with a pH test strip to be approximately 8. As before for PDADMAC, the PEI layer formation was verified by zeta potential measurements and heterocoagulation with Fe₃O₄ NPs. The results of the PEI coating can be found in Figure 34 - Figure 37.

Figure 34: A) SEM image of sample AgPFPEI-1-Fe₃O₄, made from AgPF-8; B) SEM image of sample AgPPEI-2-Fe₃O₄ made from AgP-13, both 50 k magnification, 5 kV.

Sample AgPFPEI-1 was prepared from AgPF-8 and represents the behaviour of PEI on functionalised Ag while AgPPEI-2 corresponds to a PEI coated sample AgP-13. In Figure 34 it is clearly visible, that the Fe_3O_4 NPs cover the whole patchy particles including the Ag patches in both cases. AgPFPEI-1, the functionalised and coated particles (Figure 34 A), have more Fe_3O_4 attached to them than AgPPEI-2 (Figure 34 B). The STEM images of AgPFPEI-1- Fe_3O_4 confirm the full coverage by Fe_3O_4 NPs (Figure 35 and Figure 36). Especially in the images taken with the DF4 detector (B), the fuzzy layer of varying thickness surrounding the particles is visible. The dark dots in the BF (A) or white dots in the DF (B), respectively, can be found on SiO_2 and Ag patch indifferently. The hazy look of the smaller Ag patches in Figure 36 (A2) also indicates that the Fe_3O_4 NPs cover the patches.

Figure 35: STEM exemplary images of the sample AgPFPEI-1- Fe_3O_4 . A) BF; B) DF, DF4 detector; C) HAADF. 130 x magnification, scale bar corresponds to 200 nm.

Figure 36: Collection of STEM images of sample AgPFPEI-1-Fe₃O₄. A) BF; B) DF, DF4 detector; C) HAADF. 130 x magnification, scale bar corresponds to 200 nm.

Figure 37: UV-Vis-NIR spectra normalised to 300 nm of samples AgPF-8, AgP-13 (diluted), AgPFPEI-1 (AgPF-8 + PEI) and AgPPEI-2 (AgP-13 + PEI, diluted) (left); Zeta potentials of samples AgPF-8, AgP-13, AgPFPEI-1, AgPPEI-2 (right). Unknown concentrations.

The zeta potentials in Figure 37 (right) show the successful potential reversal from -54.9 ± 6.8 mV to $+52.4 \pm 7.1$ mV and -67.1 ± 5.4 mV to $+47.5 \pm 7.1$ mV for functionalised and non-functionalised particles, respectively. None of the samples lost its blue tint upon PEI addition. The spectrum of the particles before and after PEI coating are compared in the spectrum in Figure 37. The AgPF-8 with EtOH as their medium show the highest extinction in the IR which makes it difficult to compare it to the other samples dispersed in water as was determined in section 4.1.2. From the samples in water, AgP-13 shows the most prominent broad peak in the near IR while for the PEI samples, especially AgPFPEI-1, the extinction becomes lower. The shape of the AgPFPEI-1 spectrum might furthermore express a red shift, which can only be assumed as a measurement of wavelengths further in the IR was not possible due to the absorption of water.

It might seem contradictory at first, that the particles without DDT, namely AgPPEI-2, show less Fe_3O_4 coverage, but as the Ag patches and the SiO_2 alike are covered more in Fe_3O_4 NPs for AgPFPEI-1, the reason is likely a difference in particle concentration of the two samples AgP-13 and AgPF-8 due to particle losses during washing, while the Fe_3O_4 concentration was kept constant. In any case, the PEI seems to have covered the whole particle including the Ag patches indifferently to whether there was DDT or not attached to the Ag. These findings are also reflected in the UV-Vis-NIR spectra, as the LSPR of the Ag patches seems to be less pronounced given the lower extinction. As LSPR is also dependent on the medium surrounding the metal NP

surface, the PEI layer on the Ag patch could very likely cause such a decline in the measured UV-Vis-NIR spectrum or even a shift of the peak if the resonance frequency changes due to the new medium and consequently new dielectric constant. It has already been reported, that n-alkanethiols desorb from Au and Ag surfaces in high pH solutions upon applying voltage [105, 106]. Compared to the coating step in this thesis, the exposure time to the applied potential and exposure of the DDT to high pH of only seconds is short [106]. The case, that the DDT desorbs from the Ag surface over the 30 min of coating time, might be a plausible explanation, even though no potential was applied. Even if not all DDT desorbs as reported from Pesika *et al.*, the no longer chemisorbed DDT could then open holes at defects in the DDT layer for PEI to adsorb [107]. This theory must be investigated more for verification and to determine the shielding property of DDT on Ag patches dependent on pH and exposure time to different pH. In this course, PDADMAC-DDT interactions and PEI-DDT interactions can be evaluated at suitable pH. It cannot yet be ruled out, that DDT would repel PEI like PDADMAC at a neutral pH due to the formation of a hydrophobic surface [66].

4.7 Self-organisation of oppositely charged patchy particles

Lastly, the self-organisation effect of coated with non-coated patchy particles was examined. Therefore, equal volumes of bare SiO₂ suspension and SiO₂ coated in a single layer PDADMAC, both 0.5 mg mL⁻¹, were mixed as a proof of concept. Salt was not added to the solutions to prevent screening of surface charges. The initially turbid mixture became clear as particle agglomerates sedimented (Figure 38). The oppositely charged particles are attracted towards each other and coagulate. This was expected to happen for Ag patchy particles as well. AgPFPE particles were mixed with bare SiO₂ with a diameter of 1200 nm (Merck Monospher® 1200). Larger SiO₂ particles should act as centre particles with oppositely charged and functionalised Ag patchy particles as kind of satellites adsorbed to them. The difference in particle sizes was furthermore chosen to allow for a differentiation of the particles. Macroscopically, the particles agglomerated like in the SiO₂ trial run (Figure 39). UV-Vis-NIR extinction

spectra were recorded to investigate changes in the optical properties of the AgPFPE-18 upon coagulation into larger clusters (Figure 40). The particles were further looked at with an optical microscope (Figure 41).

Figure 38: Agglomerated mixture of bare and PDADMAC coated SiO₂ of 500 nm particle size (left vial) and bare SiO₂ suspension, also 500 nm (right vial).

Figure 39: A) Sample AgPFPE-18 mixed with 1200 nm SiO₂. The agglomerated particles form larger flocs which form a loose sediment; B) Sample AgPFPE-15 forming a dense sediment as comparison.

The extinction spectra of the mixture, AgPFPE-18 and the SiO₂ (Figure 40), normalised to 300 nm, show that the extinction in the NIR decreases after mixing the particles. The overall shape of the mixture is similar to the SiO₂ extinction. A shoulder at 340 nm is an indication for the formerly present peak in AgPFPE-18. The raw data of the mix shows an almost constant extinction for all measured wavelengths which supports the subjective impression of the grey colour of the mixed sample. The LSPR peaks of the patchy particles cannot be observed. The light scattering of the agglomerates seems to dominate the extinction spectrum and does not allow for conclusions about the self-organisation.

Figure 40: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of SiO₂ with particle size 1200 nm, sample AgPFPE-18 and the mixture of both, normalised to 300 nm (left) and raw data (right). The same concentrations of SiO₂ and AgPFPE-18 were used for the mix as for the separate measurements. All measured in water.

Figure 41: Transmission microscope image of AgPFPE-18 and 1200 nm SiO₂ mix; 20 x magnification in DF mode, sharpened. Top and bottom image show the same area on the slide in different planes of the droplet. Red circle: agglomerate of particles, no organised arrangement noticeable.

An exemplary microscopy image of AgPFPE-18 mixed with 1200 nm SiO₂ can be found in Figure 41. The brighter dots are the larger SiO₂ spheres, the less bright dots are the AgPFPE-18 with a diameter of 500 nm. The bottom picture shows the same area focused to another plane. The formerly bright white dots have halos caused by interferences around them, proving that the less bright dots in the upper image are not particles from other planes. The large particles scatter light more than the smaller ones. The size difference is not noticeable as the 500 nm particles are only visible due to the scattering of the light and thus probably do not appear in their proper scale. The macroscopically visible agglomerates (Figure 41, red circles) were observed under the microscope as well as clusters starting from two NPs. No conclusions could be made from these microscope images as the particles could not be properly differentiated and no repetitive patterns were found.

As observations with a 20 x magnification in the transmission microscope did not give new insights to the self-organisation of the patchy particles and bare SiO₂, a newly installed microscope capable of correlative microscopy was used. It was tested with sample AgP-14 on a glass slide to determine the feasibility and benefit of this characterisation approach. The correlated images in the optical microscope (A) and SEM (B) together with the corresponding spectrum of a particle cluster in air are shown in Figure 42. The SEM image indicates that at least one Ag patch is present in the area which was selected for the UV-Vis-NIR measurement. Nonetheless, the spectrum cannot be compared to the previous UV-Vis-NIR measurements in EtOH and water, as the particles are surrounded by air with a different refractive index. Furthermore, the patches may form a AgO₂ layer as they were not functionalised. SEM imaging could not be carried out at the usual magnifications of 25 k and 50 k as the electron accelerating voltage of 10 kV led to charging effects and the movement of particles. This caused the sample and the image to differ. This, in turn, complicated finding the same spot in the optical microscope after choosing interesting clusters and particles during SEM. It is suggested that silicon wafers are used in future investigations of AgPs as they are compatible with the optical microscope. In general, by stacking SEM images of the same area in several magnifications, the structures can be found again more easily in the optical microscope.

Figure 42: A) Optical microscope image of sample AgP-14, 100 x magnification, BF. The area imaged in the SEM is marked with a red frame. The area used for measurement of the UV-Vis-NIR spectrum (top, right) is marked with a green square. The UV-Vis-NIR spectrum is normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum values as 1; B) SEM image of the particles within the red frame of A), 2.5 k magnification, 10 kV, scale bar corresponds to 5 μm ; C) Sample holder with glass slide and sample AgP-14. The three studs marked 1, 2 and 3 allow for the alignment of the sample holder in the SEM and the optical microscope and thus correlated images.

No samples could be investigated concerning self-organisation due to the limited time of the master's thesis project. However, the correlation microscopy itself presents a promising characterisation method for the system of Ag patchy particles and allows for more direct correlations with their extinction spectra. Particles can either be investigated by SEM first and the spectrum of selected particles can be measured in the optical microscope or the other way around. Particles can first be observed dispersed in water with the optical microscope, dried and afterwards looked at with the SEM. This approach might allow to investigate the self-organisation of oppositely charged particles as drying effects must not be considered as for sole SEM imaging.

5 Conclusion and future prospects

In this thesis, functionalised silver patchy particles were regioselectively coated with the polyelectrolyte PDADMAC by the layer-by-layer technique. The starting point was an already established silver patch synthesis route with following dodecanethiol functionalisation of the silver patch. It was important for the silver patch to stay stable and keep its morphology during the coating in order to function as a template. Preferably, but not necessarily, the patch should also keep its optical properties.

Prior to regioselective coating, the silver patch synthesis in batch and the functionalisation of the silver with dodecanethiol was successfully reproduced and the functionalisation procedure was altered with respect to the course of experiments. As PDADMAC contains chloride ions that can degrade the silver patch and with reported protective properties of thiol layers, the functionalisation time with dodecanethiol was extended from formerly 30 minutes to one hour to promote full monolayer formation. This yielded satisfactory results concerning patch stability in chloride containing solutions. However, the stabilising effect of dodecanethiol on the silver patches in different media and over various periods of time should further be investigated with prospect of silver patchy particle applications in different environments.

The layer-by-layer technique was applied to functionalised silver patchy particles. The zeta potential reversal from negatively charged silica to positive values upon coating with PDADMAC confirms the successful coating. Monolayers of PDADMAC as well as PDADMAC/PSS/PDADMAC multilayers were obtained. The available “recipe” was modified to fit the needs of silver. The exposure time of the particles in a PDADMAC solution, containing chloride ions naturally, was reduced to two minutes compared to 30 minutes while still yielding equally high zeta potentials. This is especially of advantage when moving towards continuous processes. The particles coated with positively charged PDADMAC were checked for regioselectivity by coating them with a second layer of negatively charged magnetite nanoparticles. Scanning electron microscopy and scanning transmission electron microscopy

images revealed that the magnetite does not adsorb to the functionalised silver patches. Apparently, only the free silica of the patchy particles has undergone a charge reversal upon PDADMAC adsorption and thus the negatively charged magnetite only adhered to silica, sparing the silver patch. This indicates that the coating with PDADMAC was indeed regioselective. Exploiting the functionalised silver patches as templates for regioselective coating of colloidal silica with PDADMAC is thus feasible and opens doors to studies of self-organisation or controlled deposition of such optically active particles.

It was confirmed that the layer-by-layer coating with PDADMAC of non-functionalised particles, however, fails. The silver patches degrade and cannot carry out their function of a template. The stabilisation and protection of the silver patch by functionalisation is thus obligatory for PDADMAC coating.

The necessity of functionalising the silver patches before layer-by-layer coating was additionally tested with PEI, another positively charged polyelectrolyte which does not contain chloride. The location of the PEI layer was also visualised by a magnetite coating. The PEI covers silica and silver patches alike, indifferently of functionalised or non-functionalised silver. While the PDADMAC solution had a neutral pH, the PEI solution was alkaline. Therefore, a pH dependence of the dodecanethiol layer stability could be investigated as a desorption could possibly occur at different pH values. The pH of the PEI solution could also be adjusted to neutral to confirm whether the pH is the cause of the overall coating or if it is an intrinsic property of the PEI.

Lastly, oppositely charged patchy particles were mixed and self-organisation investigated. The opposite charges were obtained by using silver patchy particles coated with PDADMAC and not coated particles with negatively charged silica surface. The particles agglomerated on the macroscopic scale. The mixture was looked at in an optical transmission microscope in darkfield mode. Individual particles in smaller clusters were not distinguishable with the available magnification due to their size in nanometre range. Larger aggregates did not provide additional information except that particles agglomerate, which was already macroscopically visible. Therefore, examination of silver patchy particles was tested with a newly installed microscope which is compatible with a scanning electron microscope and with which correlative

microscopy is possible. It allows for optical microscopy, scanning electron microscopy and measurement of the reflectance spectrum of the same area of the sample and thus detailed insight to the particle properties. It was found that the reflectance spectra with high enough intensities to be detected can be measured specifically for a cluster of particles and that the presence of silver patches on these particles can be confirmed by correlated scanning electron microscope images. This means that silver patchy particles can also be selected beforehand during scanning electron microscopy and analysed without other interfering particles as it was the case until now. It provides a promising tool to investigate the individual silver patchy particles and their self-organisation.

Another observation was made in the course of the experiments and has to be looked into more. As the silver patchy particles are stored in ethanol and are transferred back to water for polyelectrolyte coating, the blue colour of the dispersion loses intensity which is confirmed by the extinction spectrum. This was the case for functionalised as well as non-functionalised silver patches. Transferring the particles back to ethanol leads to a more vibrant colour again, though the extinction values in the spectrum do not reach the initial values. The effect is thus at least partly reversible. The change in surface plasmon resonance is unlikely to be related to the refractive index of water and ethanol as they hardly differ. A chemical reaction of the silver with oxygen dissolved in water and with ethanol is suspected but needs further investigation.

In summary, the results of this thesis were successful and satisfactory. The regioselective coating of colloidal silica by the layer-by-layer technique was established and offers a basis for further studies. However, open questions concerning the functionalisation of silver patches with dodecanethiol and possible reactions of the silver with the dispersant should be investigated in the future. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy and second harmonic generation spectroscopy might be suitable to determine the changes at the silver patch surface in addition to the already applied characterisation methods.

6 References

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7 Appendix

7.1 List of chemicals

Substance	Molar mass (g mol ⁻¹)	Density (kg L ⁻¹)	CAS- number	manufacturer
1-Dodecanethiol	202.4	0.845	112-55-0	SIGMA-ALDRICH, CHEMIE GmbH
Ammonia solution 32 %	17.03 + aq	0.88	1336-21-6	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG
Ethanol absolute AnalaR NORMAPUR® ACS, Reag. Ph. Eur.	46.07	0.791	64-17-5	VWR International S.A.S.
Formaldehyde solution 37 %	30.03	1.09	50-00-0	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG
Iron Oxide Nanoparticles	N/A	N/A	N/A	Research group
Merck Monospher® 1200 for research purposes	N/A	N/A	N/A	Merck KGaA
Merck Monospher® 500 for research purposes	60.09	N/A	N/A	Merck KGaA
Poly(diallyldimethyl- ammonium chloride) solution 20 wt % in H ₂ O (PDADMAC)	100000-200000 (low molecular weight)	1.04	26062-79-3	SIGMA-ALDRICH, CHEMIE GmbH
Poly(ethylene imine) solution 50 % (w/v) (PEI)	N/A	1.08	N/A	SIGMA-ALDRICH, CHEMIE GmbH
Poly(sodium 4- styrene-sulfonate) (PSS)	70000 206.2 (monomer)	0.801	25704-18-1	SIGMA-ALDRICH, CHEMIE GmbH
Potassium chloride ≥99.5 %, p.a., ACS, ISO	74.56	1.984	EG-Nr.: 2312118	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG

Potassium nitrate ≥99%, p.a., ISO	101.11	2.1	EG-Nr.: 2318188	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG
Silver nitrate ≥99%, Ph.Eur.	169.88	N/A	EG-Nr.: 2318539	Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG

7.2 List of devices

Device	Type	Manufacturer
Axio Imager Z.2	Microscope	Zeiss
BRANSONIC® Ultrasonic Cleaner 3510E-MT	Ultrasonic bath	Branson Ultrasonics Corporation
Centrifuge 5804	Centrifuge	Eppendorf AG
FEI Titan Themis ³ 300	Scanning transmission electron microscope	Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc.
GeminiSEM 500	Scanning electron microscope	Zeiss
Lambda 950	UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotomer	PerkinElmer Inc.
Nikon eclipse Ti	Microscope	Nikon
Zetasizer NanoZS	Zetasizer	Malvern Panalytical Ltd

7.3 Calculations

The calculations made for this work are approximations. They were made to make a rough comparison or determine the range of concentrations.

7.3.1 Approximation of coverage of silica spheres

For the approximation of the SiO₂ coverage, the total SiO₂ surface of all spheres together which are present during synthesis is calculated. From the AgNO₃ concentration, the molar concentration and, eventually, mass of elemental Ag is calculated with a ratio of 1:1. The total volume of Ag is determined and the surface is calculated, assuming a completely flat deposition with 10 nm thickness. The calculation is shown for a SiO₂ end concentration of 0.084 mg mL⁻¹ in 250 mL reaction volume.

$$m_{SiO_2} = V_{SiO_2 \text{ suspension}} \cdot c_{SiO_2} = 2.1 \text{ mL} \cdot 10 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{L}} = 0.021 \text{ g}$$

The density ρ for the Merck Monospher® 500 SiO₂ spheres has been determined to 2.0639 g cm⁻³ by Andreas Völkl.

$$V_{SiO_2, tot} = \frac{m_{SiO_2}}{\rho_{SiO_2}} = \frac{0.021 \text{ g}}{2.0639 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}} = 10.17 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^3 = 10.17 \cdot 10^{-9} \mu\text{m}^3$$

The particles are assumed to have a size of $d = 500 \text{ nm}$:

$$V_{SiO_2, sphere} = \frac{1}{6} \cdot \pi \cdot d^3 = \frac{\pi \cdot (500 \text{ nm})^3}{6} = 65.45 \cdot 10^6 \text{ nm}^3 = 0.0654 \mu\text{m}^3$$

For the actual mean particle size determined to $d = 483 \text{ nm}$ (SEM) by Andreas Völkl:

$$V_{SiO_2, sphere, d=483 \text{ nm}} = 0.0590 \mu\text{m}^3$$

The total number of spheres can be calculated by dividing the total SiO₂ volume by the volume of one SiO₂ sphere.

$$N_{d=500 \text{ nm}} = 1.55 \cdot 10^{11}$$

$$N_{d=483 \text{ nm}} = 1.72 \cdot 10^{11}$$

The total SiO₂ surface is calculated by N times the surface of a single sphere:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{SiO_2,tot} &= N \cdot \pi \cdot d^2 = 1.55 \cdot 10^{11} \cdot \pi \cdot (500 \text{ nm})^2 = 1.2168 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ nm}^2 \\ &= 1.2168 \cdot 10^5 \text{ mm}^3; S_{SiO_2,tot,d=483 \text{ nm}} = 1.2608 \cdot 10^5 \text{ mm}^3 \end{aligned}$$

The mass of Ag is calculated and the volume of deposited Ag determined:

$$\begin{aligned} n_{AgNO_3} &= c_{AgNO_3 \text{ stock}} \cdot V_{AgNO_3 \text{ solution}} = 7.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mol} = n_{Ag} \\ m_{Ag} &= n_{Ag} \cdot M_{Ag} = 107,9 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot 7.5 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mol} = 8.04 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ g} \\ V_{Ag} &= \frac{m_{Ag}}{\rho_{Ag}} = \frac{8.04 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ g}}{10.49 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cm}^3}} = 7.71 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3 = 7.71 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ mm}^3 \end{aligned}$$

The surface covered by deposited Ag is determined by assuming a patch thickness of 10 nm:

$$A_{Ag} = \frac{V_{Ag}}{10 \text{ nm}} = \frac{7.71 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ mm}^3}{10 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mm}} = 7710 \text{ mm}^2$$

The coverage is calculated by dividing the area covered with Ag by the total available SiO₂ surface:

$$\begin{aligned} coverage_{d=500 \text{ nm}} &= \frac{A_{Ag}}{S_{SiO_2,tot}} = \frac{7710 \text{ mm}^2}{1.2168 \cdot 10^5 \text{ mm}^2} = 0.063 \\ coverage_{d=483 \text{ nm}} &= \frac{7710 \text{ mm}^2}{1.2608 \cdot 10^5 \text{ mm}^2} = 0.061 \end{aligned}$$

The coverage for 0.084 g L⁻¹ SiO₂ is determined to approximately 6 %. The difference between the assumed and the measured particle size is insignificant. The coverage for 0.02 g L⁻¹ is determined to 27 % by the same procedure and using a particle size of 500 nm.

7.3.2 Approximation of chloride content in 1 wt% PDADMAC:

The molecular weight (MW) of PDADMAC is given by the manufacturer. The molar mass of the monomer can be determined by adding the molar masses of the individual atoms, hydrogen, carbon, nitrogen and chlorine. The total number of monomer units equals the total number of chlorines.

$$MW_{PDADMAC} = 100000 - 200000 \text{ Da} \rightarrow M_{PDADMAC} = 100000 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}}$$

The approximation will be made for a MW of 100000 Da.

$$M_{\text{Monomer unit}} = (8 \cdot 12 + 16 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 14 + 1 \cdot 35) = 161 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}}$$

With 1 wt% $\approx 1 \text{ g L}^{-1}$:

$$\frac{1 \text{ g}}{100000 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}} \cdot \text{L}} = 0.01 \cdot 10^{-3} \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{L}} = 0.01 \text{ mM}$$

A 1 wt% of 100000 Da PDADMAC solution equals approximately 0.01 mM. It is mixed with an equal volume of patchy particles during coating and diluted to 0.005 mM end concentration.

$$N_{\text{Monomer units}/\text{Polymer chain}} = \frac{100000 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}}}{161 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mol}}} = 621$$

One 100000 Da PDADMAC chain consists of 621 units. Thus, the concentration of Cl⁻ is 621 times the concentration of PDADMAC.

$$c_{\text{Cl}^-} = 621 \cdot 0.005 \text{ mM} = 3.1 \text{ mM}$$

7.4 Supplementary images

Figure 43: SEM images of sample AgPF-3 (functionalised). Cup-like patch morphology is intact after functionalisation with DDT; 25 k magnification, 10 kV.

Figure 44 :UV-Vis-NIR spectra of AgP-3 (non-functionalised), AgPF-4 (RT, 30 min), AgPF-5 (50°C, 30 min), AgPF-6 (RT, 24h) normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum value as 1.

Figure 45: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of AgPFPE-1 and AgPFPE-2 (both functionalised and coated with PDADMAC), raw measurement data. AgPFPE-1 signal is low and not analysable when normalised. Normalisation leads to a distorted graph.

Figure 46: SEM image of sample AgPFPE-2 (functionalised & coated AgP). Ag patches are intact and mostly still attached to the SiO₂ spheres; 25 k magnification, 10 kV.

Figure 47: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of PDADMAC coated samples AgPFPE-2 (1 M KCl, 30 min), AgPFPE-3 (1 M KCl, 10 min), AgPFPE-4 (1 M KCl, 2 min), AgPFPE-5 (10 mM KCl, 2 min) and AgPFPE-6 (10 mM KCl, 10 min), raw measurement data, unknown concentrations.

Figure 48: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of AgPFPE-5 (coated with KCl) and AgPFPE-7 (coated with KNO₃) normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum value as 1.

Figure 49: UV-Vis-NIR spectra of AgP-4 ($0.084 \text{ mg mL}^{-1} \text{ SiO}_2$, 250 mL reaction volume), AgP-5 (0.05 mg mL^{-1} , 25 mL), AgP-6 (0.02 mg mL^{-1} , 25 mL), AgP-14 (0.02 mg mL^{-1} , 200 mL; diluted), normalised with minimum as 0 and maximum value as 1.

Figure 50: Comparison of colour of sample AgP-14 (left) and AgPF-8 (right). AgP-14 has been synthesised with $0.02 \text{ mg mL}^{-1} \text{ SiO}_2$ while AgPF-8 has been obtained by functionalising sample AgP-4, synthesised with $0.084 \text{ mg mL}^{-1} \text{ SiO}_2$. Sample AgP-14 shows a more intense blue colour. The samples have approximately the same particle concentrations.

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